

SAINT MARY'S UNIVERSITY
Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya

UNIVERSITY RESEARCH CENTER

Intergenerational Relationships and Academic Well-being: The Case of Sophomore Students in a Catholic University

Research submitted by:

Dr. Liberty A. Rosario
Lead Researcher

Engr. Candido Joseph T. Rosario Jr.
Dr. Henry F. Gamboa
Mrs. Judith P. Daguio
Collaborators

August 2020

I. Title:
Intergenerational Relationships and Academic Well-being: The Case of Sophomore Students in a Catholic University

II. Abstract:

This study explored the love in the family that is manifested in the quality of intergenerational relationships experienced by sophomore students-prime contributor that affect and influence their academic well-being. Overlapping relationships with their parents, adult children, grandparents, siblings and the rest of their social structure in the educative process are paramount factors that influenced their academic well-being with the 4Rs component namely: respect, responsibility, reciprocity and resiliency. Dominantly, the component of responsibility surfaced as the underpinning stamp for the intergenerational relationships to thrive and flourish in sustaining their academic well-being. Hence, significant correlation between the quality of intergenerational relationships and academic well-being was noted. The result revealed that there was a very strong quality of intergenerational relationships noted among the four components of responsibility, resilience, reciprocity and respect that significantly made relevant relationship with the students' academic well-being which was rated strong. Having noted the ratings derived and culled from the results it was very evident that the respondents' quality of intergenerational relationships was positively correlated and influenced by the level of academic well-being. This correlation showed that the higher the IR, the better the academic well-being. Further, this reveals that the higher the quality of the four Rs, the higher or the stronger the quality of academic well-being. Strikingly, the quality of experiences of the intergenerational relationships along the four Rs was rated very strong. In relation to academic well-being, data reveals that such is fostered by the kind of support received from the family. Diversified experiences and challenges were also surfaced and became the basis for crafting intensified intervention in class through profiling of students in the classroom specifically among freshmen.

Key words: well-being, intergenerational relationship, quality

III. Research Agenda

Love in the family as manifested in intergenerational relationships: pathway towards academic well-being

IV. Name of Proponents/ Researchers

Dr. Liberty A. Rosario
Engr. Candido Joseph T. Rosario Jr.
Dr. Henry F. Gamboa
Mrs. Judith P. Daguio

V. Mechanism Applied For: Mechanism D

CHAPTER I

The Problem and Its Background

A. Rationale

Intergenerational relationships more than ever combines diversified bonds in the family ranging from the young to the old. These bonds encompass the personal relations between the members of multiple or different generations. American Heritage Dictionary (2000) defines intergenerational as "being or occurring between generations", moreover, "pertaining to or for individual in different generations or age categories". Further, Brownell and Resnick (2004) opined that intergenerational focuses on the relationships between individual members of different generations.

The existence of intergenerational relationships inevitably sustains and perpetuates the evolution of a family - for without it, no social processes may take place and several needs are not responded. This phenomenon is seen paramount as it serves as the bloodline among the various members. Provision of several concerns and issues are specifically achieved with the network of support provided in the family.

Intergenerational relationships include aspects of respect, responsibility, reciprocity and resiliency which are considered lofty family virtues that define the relevance and importance of such structure. Tim and Ellie Brubaker (1999) affirmed that the occurrence of the "The Four Rs" of respect, responsibility, reciprocity and resilience are very relevant to all forms of families and to persons who work with older people and their families. These qualities can be foundations for bolstering and strengthening intergenerational bonds, can undergird professional practice and can be potent factors for the students to achieve academic well-being. The aspects of respect, responsibility, reciprocity, and resiliency that generally characterize intergenerational relationships shall be imbedded and illustrated as bases of describing the quality of experiences of the respondents in the proposed study specifically on the over-all quality of intergenerational relationship as rated by the respondents. Implications of these qualities for support and service provision are described from social systems and continuity perspectives. Illustrations are given of how intergenerational relationships can be enhanced through understanding of and building upon the "Four Rs".

Studies have shown that in most cases parents and adult children have relatively frequent and regular contact (Umberson 1992) in fact, 40 to 50 percent of adult children see their parent at least once a week (Rossi and Rossi 1990). In the context of students who are still dependent, it is clear that their survival is directly contingent with the relationships they have in their families. Hence, intergenerational relationships adhere to the given that every human being is related to other people, young and old ones. It points to connectedness within the family in a certain place and time. Similarly, it can also become the arena or the haven to the attainment of academic well-being.

In the current study, academic well-being is seen related to intergenerational relationships as it opens up a space for generation to learn more about each other, to understand perspectives of other generations that would lead to their holistic transformation. Further, intergenerational relationships form the learning environment and the interaction of the learners which thus sustain the pervading academic well-being.

The interrelation between academic well-being and relationships can be seen in various generations within the context of the family, for a sequence of generations in the society in an evolutionary sense of generations and for different historical generations.

The concept of academic well-being is not after all new. However, feeling good academically is associated with the hedonic tradition in describing well-being alone which emphasizes emotional states. This extensively includes positive affect such as there are feelings of joy, pleasure and satisfaction with life among those who are studying. Caleon explains "well-being is a complex multidimensional construct" which can be attributed to any satisfaction with the various aspects of life. Some might equate it with happiness and quality of life. However, it is often conceived as a combination of both the feeling good and functioning well in any circumstance confronting the person. Functioning well is associated with the eudaimonic approach of understanding well-being as going beyond positive emotional experiences to emphasize meaning, sense of purpose and self-realization ".

In the first phase of the study, the attitudes on love of work and family were further explored and it was revealed that balance was put into place because of the love sustaining the family among the employees. Burrows (2018) purported that love is the oil that eases friction, the cement that binds closer together, and the music that brings harmony. Similarly such premise is now seen connected with the attainment of academic well-being as fostered with the presence of intergenerational relationships in the family. It is along this context that the proposed study has come to inception and as an offshoot of the phase one study on love in the family where it was qualified that the sustaining element for balance in work and family has been the value of love present among the employees.

This time, the second phase linked love in the family with the premise that such is manifested in the experiences of the quality of intergenerational relationship along the four Rs namely respect, responsibility, reciprocity and resiliency among the first batch of the k to 12 curriculum, now the sophomore students for teacher education, civil engineering, accountancy and nursing programs. Such is needed to be explored to find out how well they have achieved the state of academic well-being through their experiences of intergenerational relationships. The program they have selected as well as sex definitely are seen influential in the presence and quality of intergenerational relationships inasmuch as immense demands are attached. In order for them to complete and feel secure with their choice, the support coming not only from their parents, adult children, grandparent and siblings are called for. Notwithstanding the many diverse demands of their program of specialization, it can be assumed that these are responded with the support being provided and sustained by their parents,

adult children, grandparents and siblings as well as other factors included in the social structure they are immersed to. The result of the study can become a viable arena to enhance the existing shepherding program of the university specifically to students who may not have sufficient support system coming from their families.

The existing quality of relationships experienced from the family for the sophomore students across the various schools with selected representatives respondents are definitely influential in their life as a whole. Pathway to academic well-being which is described as the state of goodness and wholeness among learners cannot exist at all without the sustaining presence of different intergenerational relationships that perpetuate and sustains it.

The Family more than ever is considered as the very root of one's being; hence thus, the quality of experiences of overlapping relationships directly influence one's academic well - being . For better and for worse, family relationships play a central role in shaping an individual's well-being across the life course (Merz, Consedine, Schulze, & Schuengel, 2009).

B. Statement of the Problems

The study served as an offshoot of the previous research on the attitudes on love of the family. This purposely explored another essential component of the family as ever evolving and changing network of intergenerational relationships attached with one's love for the family along the four Rs namely: respect, responsibility, reciprocity and resiliency. Hence thus, it determined the quality of intergenerational relationships found within the family which are paramount for the various members. The level of their academic well-being was explored. Specifically, it surfaced the quality of intergenerational relationships and academic well-being as experienced by sophomore BSED/BEEEd, BSCE, BSA and BSN students who are the first batch takers of the k to 12 reform and curriculum of Saint Mary's University Bayombong Nueva Vizcaya. Significant correlation between the respondents' quality of IR and level of academic well-being existed .

Specifically, this study answered the following:

1. What is the respondents' quality of intergenerational relationships in terms of a. respect, b. responsibility, c. reciprocity and d. resiliency. ?
2. What is the respondents' level of academic well-being?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' quality of intergenerational relationships and level of academic well-being?
4. What are the experiences as well as challenges on intergenerational relationships in the family by the sophomore students that influence or affect their academic well-being?
5. What interventions can be provided to respond to the continuing search and attainment of well-being in the educative arena?

C. Statement of Null Hypothesis

1. There is no significant difference between the mean rating on the quality of intergenerational relationships and academic well-being experienced in the family along the four Rs namely respect, responsibility, reciprocity and resiliency.

D. Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework embedded herein was followed in order to achieve the purpose and objectives of the current study. The framework lays down the theory that the family which is rooted with love is ever evolving and developing with multiple relationships that influence or leave impact on the academic well-being of the various members.

**INTERGENERATIONAL RELATIONSHIPS AND ACADEMIC WELL-BEING:
THE CASE OF SOPHOMORE STUDENTS IN A CATHOLIC UNIVERSITY**

In this study, the love in the family as manifested in the experiences of sophomore students of the quality of intergenerational relationships and the level of academic well-being in the family was surfaced vis-a vi the four Rs namely: respect, responsibility, reciprocity and resiliency. The relationship between the respondents' quality of IR and level of academic well-being was explored in so far as challenges seen influential in the occurrence of intergenerational relationships since most of them came from the k to 12 track like STEM, HUMEs and ABM which more often necessitates the support of various intergenerational relationships. Experiences and challenges were surfaced and became the bases for the intervention provided that responds to the continuing search and attainment of academic well-being. Hence, enhancement of the existing shepherding program for students in the university has been forwarded as the offshoot of the current study.

E. Scope and Delimitation

This study focused on the exploration of love in the family as manifested on the quality of intergenerational relationships experienced along the four Rs of respect, responsibility, reciprocity and resiliency and academic well-being by sophomore students across the four schools with selected program of specialization namely: teacher education, civil engineering, accountancy and nursing students of Saint Mary's University. The freshmen were not intentionally included in the study as special consideration is given to the first batch of the k to 12 curriculum graduates who for that matter experienced the first trying and transition time of academic pursuit made possible through the presence of various intergenerational relationships. Personal experiences as well as challenges were unraveled from the selected respondents through sampling which became the basis for an intervention to the continuing attainment of academic well-being.

F. Significance of the Study

The study was seen significant as it gave revelation and confirmation that the family is indeed an arena for intergenerational relationships in the holistic achievement of academic well-being among various members in the family. This study based on the results revealed that love in the family which was the focus of the first phase of the study among employees of SMU can as well be manifested in the quality of existing intergenerational relationships experienced along the four Rs namely respect, responsibility, reciprocity and resiliency by sophomore students and can be a pathway in the development of their academic well-being.

Interestingly, the study is beneficial and useful to the students of the 21st century as the respondents have come into terms of their current intergenerational relationship in the family along the four Rs namely respect, responsibility, reciprocity and resiliency. It served as a diagnostic scheme to find out what intervention can be crafted to enhance the existing shepherding

program of the university. It can be an entry point to know better the students specially the level of their academic well-being along with the quality of the four Rs of intergenerational relationships.

Moreover, the selected respondents who are the sophomore and first batch of the k to 12 curriculum realized that the attainment of their academic well-being is directly dependent with the intergenerational relationships built within the family.

Parents, adult children, grandparents and siblings who may directly or indirectly leave impact on the total well-being of their children in the tertiary level. Teachers in the educative process and facilitators of learning who regularly keep in touch with the learners may determine their entry point whenever dealing with their students.

The study became the basis of providing responsive intervention towards the development of academic well-being among students. It may serve as the entry point for academic personnel to shepherd their students who may be having some problems related to the presence or absence of intergenerational relationships from which students get their support, love and academic well-being.

G. Definition of Terms

In this study, the following key terms and concepts, operationally and conceptually or theoretically defined were significant:

Academic well-being refers to the state or condition relevant to the readiness, motivation and attitude of the respondents in the academic endeavor they are into. It is the holistic state of satisfaction, academic readiness, health, happiness and sound mind emanating among individuals or students in the educative arena.

Adult children refers to the members of the family who are not adolescents anymore.

Family operationally refers to the basic institution of the society where individuals belong with varied relationships attached.

Grandparents refer to the parents of their parents in the family.

Intergenerational relationships refer to relationships that are developed and continually evolved within the context of the family structure. It is the merging and combination of persons bonded with blood ties across ages and generation.

Love refers to the binding value that sustains the family.

Parents refer to their mothers and mothers by blood relations.

Respect refers to the ability to look up to someone with admiration, care and authority.

Responsibility refers to the ability to respond in any circumstance or situation confronting the family beyond duty and obligation

Reciprocity refers to the virtue which exemplifies two way bonding in terms of responsibility and

Resiliency refers to the capability of the family to develop strategies to deal with any change and circumstance confronting the family. It features the capability to withstand and manage whatever is ahead.

Relationships refer to the number of interactions pervading in the family. Sibling/s refer to their brothers and sisters living with them.

CHAPTER II

Review of Related Literature and Studies

This study considered the following works, concepts, and ideas from different sources that were substantially useful in the analysis and expositions as well as in guiding the researchers achieved their objectives. It cannot be discounted that the family exists with various experiences relevant to the diversified composition of intergenerational relationships that are formed. The uniqueness of each family is quite dependent on quality and quantity of interactions formed.

Inasmuch as the family features the spontaneous development of intergenerational relationships, much consideration has to be taken into account as these connections which redefine if not reuel existing support group for the first batch students of the k to 12 curriculum. . Inevitably, it is clear that since the formation and beginning of the family with its unique structure provides connections between generations and have been one of the most important social bonds in all societies. Timothy H. Brubaker and Ellie Brubaker (1999) mentioned that there are four Rs that characterize intergenerational relationships within the family which sustain the emergence of bonds ranging from the young to the old.

A. Four Rs of Intergenerational Relationships

a. Respect

This is a very important ingredient that assures perpetuation of intergenerational relationships. Younger generations evidence respect for older generations in numerous ways. As younger generations experience the usual benchmarks of maturation such as getting married, living independently, becoming parents, and developing a work pattern, relationships between the generations tend to become closer (Belsky & Rovine, 1984; Suito & Pillemer, 1988; Roberts, Richards, & Bengtson, 1991). The challenges and joys of marriage, independent residence, employment and adulthood encourage younger generations to recognize the strengths and weaknesses of older generations and, as a result, many younger family members develop a respect for their parents and grandparents.

During the adolescent and early adult years, younger persons may not be cognizant of the respect they hold for their elders. They may minimize the relevancy of the older generations' information because the younger generation feels more contemporary. But, as the younger generation experiences typical life events (marriage, work, parenthood), a renewed respect for family elders often ensues. Requesting advice from parents and grandparents, visiting grandparents, inquiring about parents' and grandparents' lives, and valuing relationships with older members of the family are manifestations of the respect younger generations have for older family members.

It is respect for intergenerational relationships that provides some explanation for the importance younger family members place on relationships with older generations. College students and young adults consistently indicate that relationships with grandparents are important to them. They respect their lineage, and younger persons have emotional ties to their older generations. For example, deference to older persons at family get-togethers, expressed by placing them in seats of honor or preparing meals as the elder generation prepared meals are demonstrations of the respect younger generations have for older generations.

b. Responsibility

Being able to respond to any circumstance confronting the family connotes responsibility in any form of relationship. While children may be younger, it is spontaneous for them to foster a sense of responsibility to their elderlies. For several decades, research in gerontology and family studies has reported younger generations' feelings of responsibility for older generations who are their kin (Suito, Pillemer, Keeton, & Robison, 1996). Filial responsibility defined as "a sense of personal obligation for the well-being of aging parents" (Hamon, 1996, p. 2), is felt by younger generations. In other words, adult children and grandchildren have a sense of obligation for their parents and grandparents. It is typical for young adults to express a desire to provide assistance if their parents need it in the future. Within families in the Philippine context and culture, it is typical for the younger generation to believe that they are responsible to provide some support to their older relatives, and many are conscious of this responsibility when they make major life decisions such as where they will live.

Adult children make extraordinary sacrifices in supporting older relatives because they feel responsible to provide care. More often than not, responsibility may be grounded in a feeling of obligation or "pay back" for all the older generation previously did for the younger generation. It is typical for adult children to say "it is payback time to our elderlies". For some, parenting is rewarded by the receipt of care in the later years, and the responsibility for such care is embedded within the family's values. For others, the sense of responsibility is based upon feelings of affection for the older persons. Feelings of love are translated into a sense of responsibility to care for an older parent. In a study of caregivers for older parents with dementia, Briggs (1998) reported finding that some caregivers feel that the sense of responsibility is basic to their parent-child relationship. "It is not a responsibility that can be mitigated by extenuating circumstances in the adult child's life. Other things may need to be worked out, but this caregiving responsibility becomes the priority" (Briggs, 1998, p. 8). Regardless of the motivation (obligation, affection, or a combination of both), it is clear that younger generations have a sense of responsibility to provide assistance to older relatives.

This responsibility may differ depending on the need. For example, most middle class persons within the Philippines and other places around the globe hold a sense of responsibility for the socio-emotional needs of older relatives. Visiting, corresponding, telephoning, and e-mailing are a few examples of ways in which younger generations fulfill the responsibility that they feel. In so doing, they provide socio-emotional support to their older relatives. The attention given to older persons informs them that they are important to the younger generation. When an older relative has physical

limitations, it is expected that younger relatives will be willing to provide transportation, help with meals and other personal needs, medication, and do other tasks that assist the older person with daily living. Feelings of intergenerational responsibility are translated into action within many families in the Philippines and United States among others.

c. Reciprocity

Like any other relationship, throughout most of life, intergenerational relationships are characterized by reciprocity. The arrangement is two-way in nature. While younger generations support older relatives, older relatives are assisting younger persons. In short, intergenerational relationships in the later years are a two-way street. The classic example that many people readily observe is the child care provided by many grandparents and the emotional support adult children and grandchildren give to the grandparents.

Even in intense caregiving situations, reciprocal relationships exist. Parents tell their adult caregivers that they love and appreciate them, and such emotional reinforcement can ease the burden of caregiving. Burton (1992) reported that urban African American grandmothers sacrificed to provide care for their grandchildren and they received love and attention from their grandchildren. The reciprocal relationship between the generations is illustrated by the effects one generation has on another. Suitor, et al., (1996) report that life transitions (e.g., marriage divorce, child birth) experienced by adult children affect the lives of older persons and, in return, life changes (e.g., retirement, widowhood) have an impact on the younger generations. Intergenerational relationships are characterized by interdependency. Consequently, the relationships between the generations are often reciprocal.

d. Resiliency

The resiliency of intergenerational relationships can be illustrated by the ways in which families develop strategies to deal with change within the family. For example, when divorce and remarriage occur within any generation, the intergenerational relationships are affected. Johnson (1988) found that middle class families experienced different kinship patterns after divorce. Paternal grandparents experienced a decline in support. However, in another study Johnson & Barer (1987) reported that paternal grandmothers increased their kin networks because they continued contact with the former daughters-in-law and added the new daughter-in-law to the kin network. The differing ways of dealing with the changes because of divorce underscore the resiliency of intergenerational relationships.

Provision of care for older generations and the times when older generations become primary caregivers for grandchildren demonstrate the resiliency of intergenerational relationships. Burton (1992) and Minkler, Rose and Price (1992) provide data on surrogate parenting by older generations. Older persons, who have already parented, step in to parent when the younger generation is unable to do so. The resiliency of the intergenerational relationships provides a continuous emotional and physical support system to the youngest generation.

B. Academic Well-being

It can be noted that in recent years, several definitions on academic well-being have mushroomed which have become paramount (Ben-Arieh and Fronas, 2011). While it is true that a framework can guide the development of quality academic well-being, it may generally leave the impression that anyone who is subjected to any educational activity is someone who feels happy, contented and unafraid to go to school because of the feeling of the existence of readiness. Indicators, depend upon a grounded conceptualization of academic well-being, but also on an understanding of the school environment as well as the presence of support system provided for in the family. A student may continually experience academic well-being in so far as there is strong and unwavering assurance of the support provided for by his or her family members. The existing intergenerational relationships are strong components that allows positive feeling being a student.

There are parameters that would measure academic well-being among students. For students who are after excellent performance, theirs is contentment, should they achieve their goals. Too much engagement with their studies without being disturbed by outside factors and familial problems can be considered. Brown and Mitchell (1991) defined performance obstacles as factors in any environment that restrict the optimum productivity. In the school setting the assessment of academic well-being among students has been recurrent issue in the field of work and organizational psychology. Several aspects such as satisfaction, stress, and burnout have been sought.

If students are happily satisfied with their daily endeavor going to school as supported by their parents, then this can be a viable descriptor of academic -well-being. Should there be no emotional and

cognitive exhaustion, depersonalization and reduced personal accomplishment, assurance of academic well-being is in place. The presence of energy and vigor in any academic endeavor presupposes feeling of delight and interest.

C. Family relationships and academic well-being

Thomas (2017) in his study on family relationships claimed that such institutions are enduring and consequential for academic well-being across the life course. We discuss several types of family relationships—marital, intergenerational, and sibling ties—that have an important influence on well-being (Thomas). We highlight the quality of family relationships as well as diversity of family relationships in explaining their impact on well-being across the adult life course. We discuss directions for future research, such as better understanding the complexities of these relationships with greater attention to diverse family structures, unexpected benefits of relationship strain, and unique intersections of social statuses.

It is important for future research and health promotion policies to take into account complexities in family relationships, paying attention to family context, diversity of family structures, relationship quality, and intersections of social statuses in an aging society to provide resources to families to reduce caregiving burdens and benefit health and well-being.

An aging population and concomitant age-related disease underlies an emergent need to better understand factors that contribute to health and well-being among the increasing numbers of older adults in the United States. Family relationships may become even more important to well-being as individuals age, needs for caregiving increase, and social ties in other domains such as the workplace become less central in their lives (Milkie, Bierman, & Schieman, 2008). In this review, we consider key family relationships in adulthood—marital, parent-child, grandparent, and sibling relationships—and their impact on well-being across the adult life course.

We begin with an overview of theoretical explanations that point to the primary pathways and mechanisms through which family relationships influence academic well-being, and then we describe how each type of family relationship is associated with academic well-being, and how these patterns unfold over the adult life course. In this article, we use a broad definition of well-being, including multidimensions such as general happiness, life satisfaction, and good mental and physical health to reflect the breadth of this concept's use in the literature. We explore important directions for future research, emphasizing the need for research that takes into account the complexity of relationships, diverse family structures, and intersections of structural locations.

A life course perspective draws attention to the importance of linked lives, or interdependence within relationships, across the life course (Elder, Johnson, & Crosnoe, 2003). Family members are linked in important ways through each stage of life, and these relationships are an important source of social connection and social influence for individuals throughout their lives (Umberson, Crosnoe, & Reczek, 2010). Substantial evidence consistently shows that social relationships can profoundly influence well-being across the life course (Umberson & Montez, 2010). Family connections can provide a greater sense of meaning and purpose as well as social and tangible resources that benefit well-being (Hartwell & Benson, 2007; Kawachi & Berkman, 2001).

The quality of family relationships, including social support (e.g., providing love, advice, and care) and strain (e.g., arguments, being critical, making too many demands), can influence well-being through psychosocial, behavioral, and physiological pathways. Stressors and social support are core components of stress process theory (Pearlin, 1999), which argues that stress can undermine mental health while social support may serve as a protective resource. Prior studies clearly show that stress undermines health and well-being (Thoits, 2010), and strains in relationships with family members are an especially salient type of stress. Social support may provide a resource for coping that dulls the detrimental impact of stressors on well-being (Thoits, 2010), and support may also promote well-being through increased self-esteem, which involves more positive views of oneself (Fukukawa et al., 2000). Those receiving support from their family members may feel a greater sense of self-worth, and this enhanced self-esteem may be a psychological resource, encouraging optimism, positive affect, and better mental health (Symister & Friend, 2003). Family members may also regulate each other's behaviors (i.e., social control) and provide information and encouragement to behave in healthier ways and to more effectively utilize health care services (Cohen, 2004; Reczek, Thomeer, Lodge, Umberson, & Underhill, 2014), but stress in relationships may also lead to health-compromising behaviors as coping mechanisms to deal with stress (Ng & Jeffery, 2003). The stress of relationship strain can result in physiological processes that impair immune function, affect the cardiovascular

system, and increase risk for depression (Graham, Christian, & Kiecolt-Glaser, 2006; Kiecolt-Glaser & Newton, 2001), whereas positive relationships are associated with lower allostatic load (i.e., “wear and tear” on the body accumulating from stress) (Seeman, Singer, Ryff, Love, & Levy-Strom, 2002). Clearly, the quality of family relationships can have considerable consequences for well-being.

A life course perspective has posited marital relationships as one of the most important relationships that define life context and in turn affect individuals’ well-being throughout adulthood (Umberson & Montez, 2010). Being married, especially happily married, is associated with better mental and physical health (Carr & Springer, 2010; Umberson, Williams, & Thomeer, 2013), and the strength of the marital effect on health is comparable to that of other traditional risk factors such as smoking and obesity (Sbarra, 2009). Although some studies emphasize the possibility of selection effects, suggesting that individuals in better health are more likely to be married (Lipowicz, 2014), most researchers emphasize two theoretical models to explain why marital relationships shape well-being: the marital resource model and the stress model (Waite & Gallagher, 2000; Williams & Umberson, 2004). The marital resource model suggests that marriage promotes well-being through increased access to economic, social, and health-promoting resources (Rendall, Weden, Favreault, & Waldron, 2011; Umberson et al., 2013). The stress model suggests that negative aspects of marital relationships such as marital strain and marital dissolutions create stress and undermine well-being (Williams & Umberson, 2004), whereas positive aspects of marital relationships may prompt social support, enhance self-esteem, and promote healthier behaviors in general and in coping with stress (Reczek, Thomeer, et al., 2014; Symister & Friend, 2003; Waite & Gallagher, 2000). Marital relationships also tend to become more salient with advancing age, as other social relationships such as those with family members, friends, and neighbors are often lost due to geographic relocation and death in the later part of the life course (Liu & Waite, 2014).

Married people, on average, enjoy better mental health, physical health, and longer life expectancy than divorced/separated, widowed, and never-married people (Hughes & Waite, 2009; Simon, 2002), although the health gap between the married and never married has decreased in the past few decades (Liu & Umberson, 2008). Moreover, marital links to well-being depend on the quality of the relationship; those in distressed marriages are more likely to report depressive symptoms and poorer health than those in happy marriages (Donoho, Crimmins, & Seeman, 2013; Liu & Waite, 2014; Umberson, Williams, Powers, Liu, & Needham, 2006), whereas a happy marriage may buffer the effects of stress via greater access to emotional support (Williams, 2003). A number of studies suggest that the negative aspects of close relationships have a stronger impact on well-being than the positive aspects of relationships (e.g., Rook, 2014), and past research shows that the impact of marital strain on health increases with advancing age (Liu & Waite, 2014; Umberson et al., 2006).

Prior studies suggest that marital transitions, either into or out of marriage, shape life context or affect well-being (Williams & Umberson, 2004). National longitudinal studies provide evidence that past experiences of divorce and widowhood are associated with increased risk of heart disease in later life especially among women, irrespective of current marital status (Zhang & Hayward, 2006), and longer duration of divorce or widowhood is associated with a greater number of chronic conditions and mobility limitations (Hughes & Waite, 2009; Lorenz, Wickrama, Conger, & Elder, 2006) but only short-term declines in mental health (Lee & Demaris, 2007). On the other hand, entry into marriages, especially first marriages, improves psychological well-being and decreases depression (Frech & Williams, 2007; Musick & Bumpass, 2012), although the benefits of remarriage may not be as large as those that accompany a first marriage (Hughes & Waite, 2009). Taken together, these studies show the importance of understanding the lifelong cumulative impact of marital status and marital transitions.

Gender is a central focus of research on marital relationships and well-being and an important determinant of life course experiences (Bernard, 1972; Liu & Waite, 2014; Zhang & Hayward, 2006). A long-observed pattern is that men receive more physical health benefits from marriage than women, and women are more psychologically and physiologically vulnerable to marital stress than men (Kiecolt-Glaser & Newton, 2001; Revenson et al., 2016; Simon, 2002; Williams, 2004). Women tend to receive more financial benefits from their typically higher-earning male spouse than do men, but men generally receive more health promotion benefits such as emotional support and regulation of health behaviors from marriage than do women (Liu & Umberson, 2008; Liu & Waite, 2014). This is because within a traditional marriage, women tend to take more responsibility for maintaining social connections to family and friends, and are more likely to provide emotional support to their husband, whereas men are more likely to receive emotional support and enjoy the benefit of expanded social networks—all factors that may promote husbands’ health and well-being (Revenson et al., 2016).

However, there is mixed evidence regarding whether men's or women's well-being is more affected by marriage. On the one hand, a number of studies have documented that marital status differences in both mental and physical health are greater for men than women (Liu & Umberson, 2008; Sbarra, 2009). For example, Williams and Umberson (2004) found that men's health improves more than women's from entering marriage. On the other hand, a number of studies reveal stronger effects of marital strain on women's health than men's including more depressive symptoms, increases in cardiovascular health risk, and changes in hormones (Kiecolt-Glaser & Newton, 2001; Liu & Waite, 2014; Liu, Waite, & Shen, 2016). Yet, other studies found no gender differences in marriage and health links (e.g., Umberson et al., 2006). The mixed evidence regarding gender differences in the impact of marital relationships on well-being may be attributed to different study samples (e.g., with different age groups) and variations in measurements and methodologies.

More research based on representative longitudinal samples is clearly warranted to contribute to this line of investigation. Some recent studies among older adults suggest that relationship strain actually benefit certain dimensions of well-being. These studies suggest that strain with a spouse may be protective for certain health outcomes including cognitive decline (Xu, Thomas & Umberson, 2016).

D. Challenges on Intergenerational relationships

Diversified challenges are found in any existing intergenerational relationships more so if the age gap among the various members may be extremely wide. Among adolescents who are yet going to school, many of their choices and values reflect irreconcilable differences, hence along this context, managing relationships may be of great concern as there could be tensions and conflicts that may surface. It could be a problem surmounting the decisions of parents for and against their children or hostility among the various members in the family. Academic concerns may not be attended by elderly parents or even anyone from the family expected to provide support.

Service provision to intergenerational families requires an awareness of the respect, responsibility, reciprocity, and resiliency which characterize older family relationships. Service providers working with intergenerational families benefit from viewing those families from social systems and continuity paradigms.

The social systems perspective acknowledges the frequent changes to which social systems must successfully respond in order to maintain their structure as a system. Intergenerational families are constantly placed in situations which call for adaptation and adjustment so that they can continue their functioning as a family. For example, the illness of an older family member may result in the adaptation of caregiving by a younger family member, most likely a daughter as normally practiced in the Philippines. The older family member must also adjust by accepting the help of the daughter. The daughter may need to make adaptations at her place of employment and in her own family, with her spouse and children, in order to provide the caregiving needed by her mother. As older families experience changes through life transitions and occasional crises, they evidence resilience through their ability to change the balance they have retained throughout their families' lives while retaining their family structure. It is through intergenerational cooperation and the working together of many parts of the family unit that this occurs.

Viewing intergenerational families from a continuity perspective guides the professional to gather information about how an older individual and his or her family have adapted and responded to crises and transitions throughout the life of the family. This knowledge provides the practitioner with information about a particular intergenerational family's past history and can, therefore, assess their present ability to: (a) deal with life transitions and crises while evidencing respect for one another; (b) adapt to crises and life transitions by working together responsibly; (c) respond to life changes by giving to one another in a reciprocally; and (d) make necessary changes yet maintain family structure in a resilient manner. Families that in the past have responded to life situations with respect, responsibility, reciprocity, and resilience will likely continue those coping mechanisms in their present situations.

Service providers who view intergenerational families from social systems and continuity perspectives are facilitated in their work with older families as they practice. Through the delivery of services, the respect intergenerational family members hold for one another can be solidified by knowledge of family history. In the following case example, older family members are reminded of their respectful treatment of one another and supported to continue that behavior in the present.

Present family crises can be reframed as opportunities to solidify family members' respect for one another. As noted above, intergenerational families engage in caregiving activities for a variety of reasons. The responsible behavior that family members show to one another can be supported by service providers. First, service providers must acknowledge that intergenerational families may differ in the manner in which they evidence responsibility to their older members. One type of care is

not necessarily better than another. As Rowe and Kahn note, "No single type of support is uniformly effective; effectiveness depends of the appropriateness of the supportive acts to the requirements of the situation and the person" (1997, p. 438).

Second, and along these same lines, different populations carry out responsible behavior in different ways. Cultural backgrounds, ethnicity, racial experiences, and religious heritages all contribute to the manner in which responsibility to other generations of family members is enacted. Diller (1999) suggests that service providers engage in work with African American families that celebrates their uniqueness and strengths, rather than pressuring those families to engage in supportive behavior similar to other populations. Diller stresses the importance of identifying the particular traditions of each individual family within a specific population to find the roles they play in caregiving, but warns that the service provider will need to have established a trusting relationship before this can be accomplished.

Third, service providers need to be aware of each client's definition of family. Although many caregivers are women (Hamon, 1996) who are relatives (Briggs, 1998), it is not safe to assume that the primary caregiver in a particular situation is a woman, a daughter, or even a blood relative. The caregiver may be a daughter-in-law, or even fictive kin. The caregiver may also be a neighbor or church member, but with emotional and responsibility ties that resemble those of family members. The professional's support of these relationships of responsibility can result in continued or added intergenerational support for the recipient of care.

Some types of family responsibility should not be encouraged. Families may define responsible behavior as caregiving that does not result in the best care for the older member. Montenko and Greenberg suggest that "when families have a history of violence, abuse, or neglect, continued dependence may not be advisable" (1995, p. 385). Whether the service provider encourages family caregiving in these situations would depend on the level of dependence and type and extent of family behavior. Older parents may still desire to see and have a relationship with a child who has abused them, and adult children who are or have been abused or abusive may have this desire as well. The service provider needs to know family history and allow for self-determination to the extent possible, based on (a) who is the client, and (b) whether or not the client is able to give informed consent. If an abusive child wishes to continue caring for an older parent, the service provider has a responsibility to protect an older client. Also, if the older client is not able to give informed consent to the relationship, the service provider must take steps to provide service delivery in a manner which protects that client. In these cases, the best relationship may be a limited, monitored one in which the past abuser is educated and the abused individual is protected.

However, in most situations, the service provider's role is to support intergenerational responsibility among family members. Not only does this provide support that can facilitate the well-being of the older client, but it also provides rewards for younger family members, including an enhanced self-concept, feelings of worth, and a sense of belonging to the family. At the same time, caregiving can create role strain for family members, particularly women (Moen, Robison, & Fields, 1994), and they can benefit from the service provider's involvement and encouragement.

E. Reciprocal Relationships

Intergenerational families engage in reciprocal relationships. A service provider who assumes that old age means unreciprocated dependence demeans the older person and his or her ability and desire to give to family members. A role that older individuals can play in the caregiving process is to become a partner in choosing and determining the types of service they receive. The service provider who facilitates self-determination on the part of older clients will frequently find clients who are able to become partners in the service delivery process.

Programs which provide education and knowledge about quality caregiving to intergenerational families will foster self-determination and enhance the ability of members of those families to engage in reciprocal relationships with one another. The more actively family members can participate in quality caregiving, the better able they will be to provide care, encouragement, and support to one another.

Service providers with knowledge of a family's history of reciprocity can utilize that information to facilitate families in dealing with current crises and transitions by working together. In addition, the service provider can remind an older parent (who is currently receiving care from an adult child) of the care that parent provided to the child's own family at an earlier time.

The resilience of intergenerational families must be acknowledged in service provision and program development. In social systems terms, response to a crisis requires a reorganization within

the family. Older families have repeatedly shown the ability to accomplish this. The professional's responsibility is not to take over when a crisis occurs. Rather, the professional's support may be needed to allow a reorganization to occur and to be maintained. In this way, family members are more able to carry out activities of respect, responsibility, and reciprocity. Denying a family's resilience and taking over when not needed may foil the family's ability to provide care and may create feelings of failure for family members rather than a sense of success. Service providers are most effective when they allow family members, old and young, to make choices and become self-determining partners in the process.

Resiliency in later life may be an acceptance of the dependence which an older person encounters. Montenko and Greenberg (1995) have suggested that dependence in older adults differs from dependence in earlier years. "Late-life dependence is characterized by mutually enhancing relationships and by the reciprocal responsibilities evident in adulthood" (1995, p. 387). These authors suggest that adjustment to dependence is most successful when older persons embrace their dependence and evidence autonomy by choosing when to ask for care and by becoming involved in decisions which will affect their future. "The role shifts and transitions that accompany the acceptance of dependence contribute to the ongoing growth and development of the family as a whole" (Montenko & Greenberg, 1995, p. 382).

Family resilience may be most threatened when family members become overwhelmed with caregiving activities. If caregiving responsibilities have occurred suddenly, the family's attempts to reorganize may not occur quickly enough to provide the care necessary. Family members may feel that they cannot provide the care or even become involved to the necessary extent. For example, an unexpected illness of an elderly parent may have resulted in necessary, immediate, and all-encompassing care. Family members may feel that the required tasks are beyond their abilities and resources.

On the other hand, family caregiving responsibilities may have developed slowly, over a long period of time. Younger family caregivers who ran errands two years ago for older parents may currently find themselves driving their parents to doctor's appointments; in several more years, they may become involved in grocery shopping and house cleaning. Professionals need to be aware that those family members whose tasks have suddenly increased may experience feelings of being overwhelmed and need immediate information about resources to allow for shared caregiving. The support they require may differ from the less charged, but ongoing supportive services required by older families whose caregiving responsibilities have grown incrementally. By the same token, the second type of intergenerational caregiving family may experience feelings of never-ending hopelessness not yet acknowledged by the family with sudden caregiving responsibilities. In both of these situations, programs to support both the younger and older family members can function to enhance the resiliency that exists in intergenerational families.

Love of a family then is life's greatest blessing. This may be expressed and derived in diversified ways. Such is usually contingent with the various relationships embedded within. Shih (2017) opined that the last bastion of the individual to resist risks rests on the presence of intergenerational relationships as immense support and love may be derived herein. Weichold (2009) mentioned that globally we are confronted with an aging society. The proportion of older people will double by 2050 and as a consequence there will be more older people in society and older generation will tend to have even longer and more intense contact than they do today. Moreover, issues like the full realization of all individual's well-being and potentials as well as productivity in later years will gain more importance within intergenerational relationships built along love.

Obviously for centuries, in most cultures, the family has been defined by "blood relatives" and "blood relationships". Their several conjugal units of husband, wife, children and grandparents are very influential. Over time, norms and patterns have incessantly evolved in various cultures for intergenerational living arrangements, obligations, support, inheritance, and relationships.

Currently, in addition to the traditional conjugal unit, families exist in many different forms such as single parent, grandparent-grandchild, childless, same-sex couples and step and blended families. Families differ also in their housing and living patterns. These innovations and changes definitely call for new definitions and new ways to work out satisfying and workable intergenerational bonds. This proposed study includes an array of excellent experiences among respondents that explore relationships between the generations in today's families specifically among sophomore students of a university.

Further, Ames (2016) explored some implications of relationships such as of marital satisfaction, divorce, and co-residence patterns on life course parenting and delineates major themes that characterize parent-child relationships over the life course.

Similarly, Seagull (2017) presented a value-driven framework based on the core values of respect and honesty, key tools, and practical suggestions for helping two adult generations develop new ways of relating when children "come home again" or "stay connected" with the family.

In the proposed study, the framework for understanding intergenerational relations is based on the construct of generation and is set within a life course perspective that recognizes the dynamic nature of generations across time. This presupposes that once a family is initially built, the combination as well as conglomerations of various relationships ranging from young to old generation may be put into place. Indeed, the word "generation" is used in diversified ways. Historically it can mean to represent and explain as a specific catalogue or chronology of time. It can be also regarded as a source of community of diversified members. It is also considered as a way to identify injustice and as an axis of conflict and impending crisis" (Whitej 2013: 217).

Along this circumstance, the use of the term would simply mean the various relationships formed within the family among the members. It is important to clarify the use of the term because generational understanding influences and reflects societal attitudes, and informs both practice and policy related to population ageing.

Within the context of Filipino families, intergenerational relationships are consistently existing, thriving and has significantly changed the landscape of the 21st century families. Contrary to the belief that the nuclear family is most important and leads to isolation from other family units within a kinship network, intergenerational relationships are alive and well. Younger generations marry and establish nuclear family units, but they continue and sustain their relationships with the older family members.

Older generations watch their children grow, study, mature, marry and have their own children and the older generation continues to be involved in the lives of younger family members. A modified extended family pattern describes families within the Philippines. For Ilocanos, Tagalog, Gaddangs, Pangasinense, Cebuano and the rest of other diverse heritages, families are intergenerational and more often extended in nature.

As individuals live longer, their opportunities for multiple generational contact increases. For example, there is a 60 percent chance that a 60 year old female will have a living parent (Watkins, Menken, & Bongaarts, 1987), and it is likely that she is also a grandparent (Robertson, 1996). These intergenerational relationships are characterized by respect, responsibility, reciprocity and resiliency. Regardless of the generation (older, middle, and younger) of focus, respect, responsibility, reciprocity, and resiliency are evident within the relationships, and these characteristics are relevant to individuals who work with older people and their families. These characteristics can be used as foundations on which to further strengthen intergenerational bonds.

It is purported that children and parents tend to remain closely connected to each other across the life course, and it is well-established that the quality of intergenerational relationships is central to the well-being of both generations (Merz, Schuengel, & Schulze, 2009; Polenick, DePasquale, Eggebeen, Zarit, & Fingerman, 2016). In the proposed study, while the sophomore students who are the first batch of the k to 12 curriculum are quite older and assumingly graduates already of the previous curriculum, overlapping relationships still evolve as they so not separate from their parents, siblings and grandparents. Direct support actually come from the intergenerational relationships they have been attached to over the years.

Moreover, recent research also points to the importance of relationships with grandchildren for aging adults (Mahne & Huxhold, 2015). Hence, the conducted study I focused on the intergenerational relationships experienced in the family among parents, adult children, and grandparents as experienced by students that contribute to their well-being.

Notably, parents, grandparents, and children often provide care for each other at different points in the life course, which can contribute to social support, stress, and social control mechanisms that influence the health and well-being of each in important ways over the life course (Nomaguchi & Milkie, 2003; Pinquart & Soerensen, 2007; Reczek, Thomeer, et al., 2014).

Relationships with family members are significant for well-being across the life course (Merz, Consedine, et al., 2009; Umberson, Pudrovska, et al., 2010). As individuals age, family relationships often become more complex, with sometimes complicated marital histories, varying relationships with children, competing time pressures, and obligations for care. At the same time, family relationships become more important for well-being as individuals age and social networks diminish even as family

caregiving needs increase. Stress process theory suggests that the positive and negative aspects of relationships can have a large impact on the well-being of individuals.

Family relationships provide resources that can help an individual cope with stress, engage in healthier behaviors, and enhance self-esteem, leading to higher well-being. However, poor relationship quality, limited financial resources, incapacity to send children to school, parental abandonment, intense caregiving for family members, unsupportive parents and marital dissolution are all stressors that can take a toll on an individual's well-being. Moreover, family relationships also change over the life course, with the potential to share different levels of emotional support and closeness, to take care of us when needed, to add varying levels of stress to our lives, and to need caregiving at different points in the life course.

The potential risks and rewards of these relationships have a cumulative impact on health and well-being over the life course. Additionally, structural constraints and disadvantage place greater pressures.

E. Intergenerational Relationships

Intergenerational relationships within the Filipino culture and across the globe are generally marked by respect, responsibility, reciprocity, and resiliency. Throughout the family history, younger, middle, and older generations develop ways to support one another in the later years. In fact, as the generations' age, the intergenerational connections become more important. The intergenerational bonds provide a framework for service providers to support families in the later years.

Contextually, family structure in the Philippines context is generally extended in nature though changes have been noted with the increase of nuclear families. Nevertheless, connection and linkages with older family members are tangibly in place.

Children and parents tend to remain closely connected to each other across the life course, and it is well-established that the quality of intergenerational relationships is central to the well-being of both generations (Merz, Schuengel, & Schulze, 2009; Polenick, DePasquale, Eggebeen, Zarit, & Fingerman, 2016). Recent research also points to the importance of relationships with grandchildren for aging adults (Mahne & Huxhold, 2015). We focus here on the well-being of parents, adult children, and grandparents. Parents, grandparents, and children often provide care for each other at different points in the life course, which can contribute to social support, stress, and social control mechanisms, that influence the health and well-being of each in important ways over the life course (Nomaguchi & Milkie, 2003; Pinquart & Soerensen, 2007; Reczek, Thomeer, et al., 2014).

a. Parents

Family scholarship highlights the complexities of parent-child relationships, finding that parenthood generates both rewards and stressors, with important implications for well-being (Nomaguchi & Milkie, 2003; Umberson, Pudrovska, & Reczek, 2010). Parenthood increases time constraints, producing stress and diminishing well-being, especially when children are younger (Nomaguchi, Milkie, & Bianchi, 2005), but parenthood can also increase social integration, leading to greater emotional support and a sense of belonging and meaning (Berkman, Glass, Brissette, & Seeman, 2000), with positive consequences for well-being. Studies show that adult children play a pivotal role in the social networks of their parents across the life course (Umberson, Pudrovska, et al., 2010), and the effects of parenthood on health and well-being become increasingly important at older ages as adult children provide one of the major sources of care for aging adults (Seltzer & Bianchi, 2013). Norms of filial obligation of adult children to care for parents may be a form of social capital to be accessed by parents when their needs arise (Silverstein, Gans, & Yang, 2006).

Although the general pattern is that receiving support from adult children is beneficial for parents' well-being (Merz, Schulze, & Schuengel, 2010), there is also evidence showing that receiving social support from adult children is related to lower well-being among older adults, suggesting that challenges to an identity of independence and usefulness may offset some of the benefits of receiving support (Merz et al., 2010; Thomas, 2010). Contrary to popular thought, older parents are also very likely to provide instrumental/financial support to their adult children, typically contributing more than they receive (Grundy, 2005), and providing emotional support to their adult children is related to higher well-being for older adults (Thomas, 2010). In addition, consistent with the tenets of stress process theory, most evidence points to poor quality relationships with adult children as detrimental to parents' well-being (Koropecjy-Cox, 2002; Polenick et al., 2016); however, a recent study found that strain with adult children is related to better cognitive health among older parents, especially fathers (Thomas & Umberson, 2017).

b. Adult Children

As children and parents age, the nature of the parent-child relationship often changes such that adult children may take on a caregiving role for their older parents (Pinquart & Soerensen, 2007). Adult children often experience competing pressures of employment, taking care of their own children, and providing care for older parents (Evans et al., 2016). Support and strain from intergenerational ties during this stressful time of balancing family roles and work obligations may be particularly important for the mental health of adults in midlife (Thomas, 2016). Most evidence suggests that caregiving for parents is related to lower well-being for adult children, including more negative affect and greater stress response in terms of overall output of daily cortisol (Bangerter et al., 2017); however, some studies suggest that caregiving may be beneficial or neutral for well-being (Merz et al., 2010). Family scholars suggest that this discrepancy may be due to varying types of caregiving and relationship quality. For example, providing emotional support to parents can increase well-being, but providing instrumental support does not unless the caregiver is emotionally engaged (Morelli, Lee, Arnn, & Zaki, 2015). Moreover, the quality of the adult child-parent relationship may matter more for the well-being of adult children than does the caregiving they provide (Merz, Schuengel, et al., 2009).

Although caregiving is a critical issue, adult children generally experience many years with parents in good health (Settersten, 2007), and relationship quality and support exchanges have important implications for well-being beyond caregiving roles. The preponderance of research suggests that most adults feel emotionally close to their parents, and emotional support such as encouragement, companionship, and serving as a confidant is commonly exchanged in both directions (Swartz, 2009). Intergenerational support exchanges often flow across generations or towards adult children rather than towards parents. For example, adult children are more likely to receive financial support from parents than vice versa until parents are very old (Grundy, 2005). Intergenerational support exchanges are integral to the lives of both parents and adult children, both in times of need and in daily life.

c. Grandparents

Over 65 million Americans are grandparents (Ellis & Simmons, 2014), 10% of children lived with at least one grandparent in 2012 (Dunifon, Ziol-Guest, & Kopko, 2014), and a growing number of American families rely on grandparents as a source of support (Settersten, 2007), suggesting the importance of studying grandparenting. Grandparents' relationships with their grandchildren are generally related to higher well-being for both grandparents and grandchildren, with some important exceptions such as when they involve more extensive childcare responsibilities (Kim, Kang, & Johnson-Motoyama, 2017; Lee, Clarkson-Hendrix, & Lee, 2016). Most grandparents engage in activities with their grandchildren that they find meaningful, feel close to their grandchildren, consider the grandparent role important (Swartz, 2009), and experience lower well-being if they lose contact with their grandchildren (Drew & Silverstein, 2007). However, a growing proportion of children live in households maintained by grandparents (Settersten, 2007), and grandparents who care for their grandchildren without the support of the children's parents usually experience greater stress (Lee et al., 2016) and more depressive symptoms (Blustein, Chan, & Guanais, 2004), sometimes juggling grandparenting responsibilities with their own employment (Harrington Meyer, 2014). Using professional help and community services reduced the detrimental effects of grandparent caregiving on well-being (Gerard, Landry-Meyer, & Roe, 2006), suggesting that future policy could help mitigate the stress of grandparent parenting and enhance the rewarding aspects of grandparenting instead.

d. Sibling relationships

Sibling relationships are understudied, and the research on adult siblings is more limited than for other family relationships. Yet, sibling relationships are often the longest lasting family relationship in an individual's life due to concurrent life spans and indeed, around 75% of 70-year olds have a living sibling (Settersten, 2007). Some suggest that sibling relationships play a more meaningful role in well-being than is often recognized (Cicirelli, 2004). The available evidence suggests that high quality relationships characterized by closeness with siblings are related to higher levels of well-being (Bedford & Avioli, 2001), whereas sibling relationships characterized by conflict and lack of closeness have been linked to lower well-being in terms of major depression and greater drug use in adulthood (Waldinger, Vaillant, & Orav, 2007). Parental favoritism and disfavoritism of children affects the closeness of siblings (Gilligan, Sutor, & Nam, 2015) and depression (Jensen, Whiteman, Fingerman, &

Birditt, 2013). Similar to other family relationships, sibling relationships can be characterized by both positive and negative aspects that may affect elements of the stress process, providing both resources and stressors that influence well-being.

Siblings play important roles in support exchanges and caregiving, especially if their sibling experiences physical impairment and other close ties, such as a spouse or adult children, are not available (Degeneffe & Burcham, 2008; Namkung, Greenberg, & Mailick, 2017). Although sibling caregivers report lower well-being than noncaregivers, sibling caregivers experience this lower well-being to a lesser extent than spousal caregivers (Namkung et al., 2017). Most people believe that their siblings would be available to help them in a crisis (Connidis, 1994; Van Volkom, 2006), and in general support exchanges, receiving emotional support from a sibling is related to higher levels of well-being among older adults (Thomas, 2010). Relationship quality affects the experience of caregiving, with higher quality sibling relationships linked to greater provision of care (Eriksen & Gerstel, 2002) and a lower likelihood of emotional strain from caregiving (Mui & Morrow-Howell, 1993; Quinn, Clare, & Woods, 2009). Taken together, these studies suggest the importance of sibling relationships for well-being across the adult life course.

The gender of the sibling dyad may play a role in the relationship's effect on well-being, with relationships with sisters perceived as higher quality and linked to higher well-being (Van Volkom, 2006), though some argue that brothers do not show their affection in the same way but nevertheless have similar sentiments towards their siblings (Bedford & Avioli, 2001). General social support exchanges with siblings may be influenced by gender and larger family context; sisters exchanged more support with their siblings when they had higher quality relationships with their parents, but brothers exhibited a more compensatory role, exchanging more emotional support with siblings when they had lower quality relationships with their parents (Voorpostel & Blieszner, 2008). Caregiving for aging parents is also distributed differently by gender, falling disproportionately on female siblings (Pinquart & Sorensen, 2006), and sons provide less care to their parents if they have a sister (Grigoryeva, 2017). However, men in same-sex marriages were more likely than men in different-sex marriages to provide caregiving to parents and parents-in-law (Reczek & Umberson, 2016), which may ease the stress and burden on their female siblings.

Substantial evidence suggests that the experience of intergenerational relationships varies for men and women. Women tend to be more involved with and affected by intergenerational relationships, with adult children feeling closer to mothers than fathers (Swartz, 2009). Moreover, relationship quality with children is more strongly associated with mothers' well-being than with fathers' well-being (Milkie et al., 2008). Motherhood may be particularly salient to women (McQuillan, Greil, Shreffler, & Tichenor, 2008), and women carry a disproportionate share of the burden of parenting, including greater caregiving for young children and aging parents as well as time deficits from these obligations that lead to lower well-being (Nomaguchi et al., 2005; Pinquart & Sorensen, 2006). Mothers often report greater parental pressures than fathers, such as more obligation to be there for their children (Reczek, Thomeer, et al., 2014; Stone, 2007), and to actively work on family relationships (Erickson, 2005). Mothers are also more likely to blame themselves for poor parent-child relationship quality (Elliott, Powell, & Brenton, 2015), contributing to greater distress for women. It is important to take into account the different pressures and meanings surrounding intergenerational relationships for men and for women in future research.

Family scholars have noted important variations in family dynamics and constraints by race-ethnicity and socioeconomic status. Lower SES can produce an exacerbate family strains (Conger, Conger, & Martin, 2010). Socioeconomically disadvantaged adult children may need more assistance from parents and grandparents who in turn have fewer resources to provide (Seltzer & Bianchi, 2013). Higher SES and white families tend to provide more financial and emotional support, whereas lower SES, black, and Latino families are more likely to coreside and provide practical help, and these differences in support exchanges contribute to the intergenerational transmission of inequality through families (Swartz, 2009). Moreover, scholars have found that a happiness penalty exists such that parents of young children have lower levels of well-being than nonparents; however, policies such as childcare subsidies and paid time off that help parents negotiate work and family responsibilities explain this disparity (Glass, Simon, & Andersson, 2016). Fewer resources can also place strain on grandparent-grandchild relationships. For example, well-being derived from these relationships may be unequally distributed across grandparents' education level such that those with less education bear the brunt of more stressful grandparenting experiences and lower well-being (Mahne & Huxhold, 2015). Both the burden of parenting grandchildren and its effects on depressive symptoms disproportionately fall upon single grandmothers of color (Blustein et al., 2004). These

studies demonstrate the importance of understanding structural constraints that produce greater stress for less advantaged groups and their impact on family relationships and well-being.

Related Studies

Research on intergenerational relationships suggests the importance of understanding greater complexity in these relationships among members. Greater attention to diverse family structures and perspectives of multiple family members may surface several issues. There is an increasing trend of individuals delaying childbearing or choosing not to bear children (Umberson, Pudrovska, et al., 2010). How might this influence marital quality and general well-being over the life course and across different social groups? Greater attention to the quality and context of intergenerational relationships from each family member's perspective over time may prove fruitful by gaining both parents' and each child's perceptions. This work has already yielded important insights, such as the ways in which intergenerational ambivalence (simultaneous positive and negative feelings about intergenerational relationships) from the perspectives of parents and adult children may be detrimental to well-being for both parties (Fingerman, Pitzer, Lefkowitz, Birditt, & Mroczek, 2008; Gilligan, Suitor, Feld, & Pillemer, 2015). Future work understanding the perspectives of each family member could also provide leverage in understanding the mixed findings regarding whether living in blended families with stepchildren influences well-being (Gennetian, 2005; Harcourt, Adler-Baeder, Erath, & Pettit, 2013) and the long-term implications of these family structures when older adults need care (Seltzer & Bianchi, 2013). Longitudinal data linking generations, paying greater attention to the context of these relationships, and collected from multiple family members can help untangle the ways in which family members influence each other across the life course and how multiple family members' well-being may be intertwined in important ways.

Other related studies also considered the impact of intersecting structural locations that place unique constraints on family relationships, producing greater stress at some intersections while providing greater resources at other intersections. For example, same-sex couples are less likely to have children (Carpenter & Gates, 2008) and are more likely to provide parental caregiving regardless of gender (Reczek & Umberson, 2016), suggesting important implications for stress and burden in intergenerational caregiving for this group. Much of the work on gender, sexuality, race, and socioeconomic status differences in intergenerational relationships and well-being examine one or two of these statuses, but there may be unique effects at the intersection of these and other statuses such as disability, age, and nativity. Moreover, these effects may vary at different stages of the life course.

While there is less research on race-ethnicity and heterogeneity, family scholars have surfaced and noted variations in sibling relationships and their effects by race-ethnicity and socioeconomic status. Lower socioeconomic status has been associated with reports of feeling less attached to siblings and this influences several outcomes such as obesity, depression, and substance use (Van Gundy et al., 2015). Fewer socioeconomic resources can also limit the amount of care siblings provide (Eriksen & Gerstel, 2002).

These studies suggest sibling relationship quality as an axis of further disadvantage for already disadvantaged individuals. Sibling relationships may influence caregiving experiences by race as well, with black caregivers more likely to have siblings who also provide care to their parents than white caregivers (White-Means & Rubin, 2008) and sibling caregiving leading to lower well-being among white caregivers than minority caregivers (Namkung et al., 2017).

According to Timbreza (2003), Filipinos families are generally family oriented. Many actions, plans and goals in life of an individual are either affected or is centered upon the family. In fact "family success is the measure of a successful life for the Filipinos. Here are some Filipino sayings that reflect how they view the family:

Boholanos: "Ang familia nga nagatanum ug kaayohan nag-ani ug kapalaran; ang nagatanum ugkadautan, nag-ani og lonlon kasakitan" (*Literally, the family that sows goodness reaps fortune; the one that sows evil reaps suffering*)

Bicolanos: "An harong man palasyo kun an laog kuwagoj marhay pa ang payag na laog tao" (*Literally, a house may be a palace, but if the owner is an owl, better is a hut where the owner is a human being*)

Tagalogs: "Mabuti pa ang kubo na ang nakatira ay tao, kaysa isang bahay na bato na ang nakatira aykuwago" (*Literally, A hut where a person lives is better than a house of stone where an owl resides.*)

Ilocanos: "Ti timpuyog ti pamilia isu't mangted ti kired ken pigsa" (*Literally, family harmony provides fortitude and strength*). "Uray awan ti kukuamj no la ket nauros ti pamiliam" (*Literally, even though you don't have property as long as you have a harmonious family*).

The definition of Filipino family and kinship structure, according to Medina (2001), is evolving as structures continue to change. One of the current definitions which encompass all types of families is "two or more persons who share resources, share responsibility for decisions, share values and goals, and have a commitment to each other over time. The function attributed to families are economic consumption, socialization of the young, and affective dimensions" This definition takes into account other family structure such as single parent/headed families, homosexual or domestic partnership types of families, live-in partners, among others. Primary importance here is placed on the issues of commitment and affection. Residence is not a criterion as there are also people who lives under one roof but are not necessarily considered a family (referred to as households). Medina describes family as "a group of persons living under one roof and sharing the same kitchen and housekeeping arrangements.

a. Nuclear and non-Nuclear Family

A nuclear family from non-nuclear family. A family is nuclear when it consists of a married man or woman with their offspring. The couples may or may not be married and their children may or may not be biological. This is considered the primary unit of all family types as other types evolve from this structure. Generally, this is accepted as universal. There are two types of nuclear families; first, the family of orientation. Which consists of the individual, parents, and siblings. This is primarily the family the "individual was born and reared;" and second, the family of procreation which consists of the individual, spouse, and their children. This is established in marriage.

It is noteworthy that the Filipino family is referred to as "mag-anak". This reflects the importance of the value of children in the family. A husband and wife relationship does not make a "mag-anak" but a "mag-asawa" status. This implies that a child/children completes the concept of family among Filipinos. Traditionally, this is how children are seen as blessings; how people perceive the husband as manly if he can produce more offspring; and how the wife is considered as finally realizing her womanhood and that she feels that her relationship with her husband is paved.

b. Conjugal Family and Consanguineal Family.

Conjugal family emphasizes the importance of marital bond. It on the immediate or nuclear family. In Consanguineal family, other blood related persons/relatives are considered just as important with the immediate ones. This reflects more the Filipino attitude towards family, that is, an exclusionary tendency, individual is affiliated at birth with a group related to the mother.

c. Rules of Residence.

Residence determines the quality and quantity of interaction with relatives for it affects the pattern of socialization among relatives and/or family members. For instance, a child who grows with his/her uncle/aunties/grandparents because his/her parents are both working abroad will be more likely emotionally attached to them than with his/her parents. The following are the basic residence rules:

Patrilocal residence happens when a newly married couple establishes their home near or in the groom's father's house. About 69% of the world's societies follow patrilocal residence, making it the most common.

Matrilocal residence happens when a newly married couple establishes their home near or in the bride's mother's house. This keeps women near their female relatives. Men leave their natal households when they marry. About 13% of the world's societies have matrilocal residence

Avunculocal residence happens when a newly married couple establishes their home near or in the groom's maternal uncle's house. Nearly 4% of the world's societies have avunculocal residence

Ambilocal residence happens when a newly married couple has the choice of living with or near the groom's or the bride's family. The couple may also live for a while with one set of parents and then move to live with the other. About 9% of the world's societies have ambilocal residence.

Neolocal residence happens when a newly married couple establishes their home independent of both sets of relatives. While only about 5% of the world's societies follow this pattern. Due to economic hardship neolocal residence becomes difficult goal to achieve, especially for young newlyweds.

Neolocal residence is found in societies in which kinship is minimized or economic considerations require moving residence periodically. For instance, employment in large corporations or the military often calls for frequent relocations, making it nearly impossible for extended families to remain together.

d. Pattern of Authority.

There are three types of authority pattern in the family:

Patriarchal wherein the oldest male, usually the father, has control over the other members.

Matriarchal wherein the mother has the authority. This however, usually goes with matrilineal residence.

Equalitarian (Egalitarian) where most Filipino families are most likely classified. Although the husband is generally referred to as the head, the wife is in charge with the money and the organization in the house and its affairs.

According to the authors, family structures and interaction in the family are dynamically changing due to economic situation and technological advancement. There is a trend to nuclearization as families are being drawn to urbanized areas to work.

Parents who go abroad to find greener pastures so to speak leave behind their children to other relatives thus shifting the authority to them which also affects how the child interacts to the society.

The decision maker which is traditionally held by the eldest male in the family is slowly fading as there is tendency for the breadwinner (most likely the working member or highest earner in the family) to assume this role though respect is still accorded to the eldest still. "Female headship has become an urban phenomenon because it is in the urban center where employment opportunities for women are more available" (Medina 2001).

Change is constant and the basic unit of society- the family- is not immune to it. It is composed of human beings & human beings naturally adapt to the environment to survive. The environment is continually changing prompting people to change their interaction with it & one another also. To this, we are challenged as Filipinos to see if the changes we welcome in our homes are actually working to our advantages- do these promote better relationships & worthwhile companionship among family members & among families in the society?

The study of Morillo et. al. (2013) entitled "Views and Values on Family among Filipinos: An Empirical Exploration" focused on an exploration on the correlates of views on family values among Filipinos, particularly those concerning the traditional nuclear family set-up, the woman's roles within family, and the reciprocal relationship of the parent and child based on the data from the World Values Survey for the Philippines in 1996 and 2001. Based on their observations, the Filipino family provides an interesting study because familism is embedded in its social sphere, translating its relational quality outside the family. This idea is based on the study of Medina (2001) Miralao (1994) that Filipino families are "family-centered, child-centric, having close ties, and a large family size.

The results of the study show that generally, Filipino families share family values, especially on those related to child rearing for both parents, and child-bearing. However, there are indications that such views also differ across educational attainment, geographic location, social class, and ethnic groups. The differences in views are reflective of shifting family values, which could help explain current polarizing policy debates on issues on the reproductive health, divorce, and migration.

Based on their analysis on survey data, the researchers were able to identify the correlates that show evidence on the convergence or divergence in views concerning family values within groups in the Philippines. The family values they investigated reflect some traditional and non-traditional Filipino perspectives on living arrangements and family composition. However, based on the results the parents need not be married, since there is indication of wide disagreement among groups about the continuing relevance of marriage as an institution. According to the researchers, the respondents also equivocate on absolute love for parents, as they do with regard to marriage. Differences in views about family values were affected by educational attainment (high school or higher), gender (male), income class (upper middle, lower class), location (urban; Luzon, Visayas), and ethnicity (Bicolano, Ilonggo, Waray, Kapampangan) and, to some extent, religion (Roman Catholic). This implies that while it is important to identify the family values that unite Filipinos, it is equally important to discern what divides them.

Furthermore, their study reveals that evolving family values manifest shifting family structures and dynamics. This means that the correlates identified can serve as bases for interventions or alternative programs from government institutions, and perhaps more research inquiry from the different fields in the social sciences. Thus, government and other policy-making institutions are given ideas in making relevant policies on education, for instance.

F. On Studies Focusing on Family relationships

This study is inspired by the Family Survey 2015 conducted by the Family Council in Hong Kong as submitted by Policy 21 Limited in 2016. The survey gathered updated and empirical information on families in Hong Kong on a biennial basis to keep track of changes and development of Hong Kong families in terms of family structures, attitudes, values, among others. Primarily, the purpose of the Family Survey 2015 is to gather relevant information and data on the existing situation of families in to ascertain the experiences of the respondents on family regarding the importance of family, parenthood, family functioning and satisfaction with family life, work-family balance, availability of social support network, transgenerational issues, and awareness and participation to family-related program. Eventually the survey made recommendations based on the results for the promotion of family core values among the people. It also made comparisons with the family survey conducted in 2011 and 2013.

The study used qualitative and quantitative methods, including focus group discussions, a territory-wide household survey and three in-depth surveys. Before the survey, literature research was also conducted in order to gather more relevant information in Hong Kong and other countries. The theoretical framework was based on experiences in other countries and the views gathered from the focus group discussions. This also provided the design of the questionnaire for the territory-wide household survey and face-to-face interviews.

On the importance of family, results of the survey indicated that most people still held to traditional family values, for instance, having a son is preferable over having a daughter to continue family name; family shame must be kept within the family; and working hard to bring honor to the family. Most of the respondents were willing to live with their parents. They are also willing to support them though they do not live with them. However most of them do not agree with living with their adult children. They consider marriage as a necessary step in life and child bearing is important in marriage. However, though they support marriage, less of them opposed cohabitation. Almost half of the respondents agreed that the best solution of married couple without children is divorce; although there was no consensus when couple already had children.

Regarding the involvement of grandparents on family matters, it is significant to note that the value of their contribution decreased, although it is still recognized. Generally, most of the respondents still practice filial piety like caring, respecting, greeting, pleasing, obeying and providing financial support to their parents.

Regarding parenthood, about half of parents consider the stress of raising children overwhelming. Most of them were not confident of their ability in raising children and managing the associated stress. Over half of parents believed they no private time for their families. Most of the parents are considered having good parenting style. For instance, most parents interviewed in the survey would set good examples for their children. They admit fault when they did wrong and explain to their children when they do something wrong. They set good examples to children so that they would respect and take care of their grandparents too. Almost half of parents agreed that grandparents have the responsibility to discipline their grandchildren. Yet slightly less than half of parents claimed that grandparents should not intervene in their parenting method.

On family functioning in relationship and family life satisfaction, it is found out that most families are functioning well. For instance, most people were quite satisfied with the relationship with their family members. Most family members were dependent on each other and their relationship with one another was fairly close in general. In general, the respondents were quite satisfied with the relationship with their family members and their family life. The survey results indicated that time spent with parents was limited, but with improvement in the past two years perhaps because increasing number of people including grandparents, parents and children frequently or sometimes used modern technologies as a mode of communication. For instance, they use modern technology like SMS and social media to express some wordings that were hard to say in sharing their feelings with their family members; update their experience in daily life;

On balancing family relationships, results of the survey reveal that relationships balance continues to remain a challenge. One quarter of those at work found it difficult to strike a balance between work and family relationships in view of competing priorities and nearly half of those at work reported stress in balancing work with family. Despite the fact that quite a number of people at work reported stress in balancing the competing demands of work and family, more than half of the respondents were satisfied with the amount of time spent at work and with family.

Some of the notable recommendations of the based on the survey include important issues for family support services because of the greater variety of family forms and continued changes in attitudes

on family values today. With the increasing number of divorce cases and their potential impact on children, educational workshops on parenting skills, marriage enrichment and marriage counselling are desired. It is recommended that these be strengthened, especially for the young adults. Family life education in child care, child rearing as well as parental and in-law relationships remain valuable for young adults. In order to minimize the adverse effects on the divorced couples and their children it is also recommended to strengthen pre- and post-divorce counselling to those couples contemplating separation and divorce. Besides the services rendered to married couples with problems, more preventive programs are recommended to be developed and promoted

Regarding the stress faced by parents in raising children which will certainly affect the quality of parenting and well-being of children, the promotion of stress management techniques among parents, like a proactive stance on stress management, is highly recommended. Stress relief programs should be sector specific to achieve better result. Regarding the aging population, it is recommended to continue to raise awareness among grandparents of the range of support available to them in the community and to continue to promote the needs for respecting and caring for our aging parents and grandparents.

Family-friendly employment practices (FFEPs), the employers or the top management of organizations and institution have to understand the trade-offs between various important activities occurring simultaneously and prioritize and allocate proper resources to avoid unnecessary tensions and work pressure. In so doing, the individuals will have more time to tackle with work and family issues effectively. Furthermore, apart from monetary benefits, a conducive and friendly working environment and job assurance is crucial for creating balance. Regarding the publicity, it is recommended to organize dialogue sessions for the business sectors (e.g. professional associations, grass-roots community groups, labor unions, etc.) to promote stress management techniques and to raise the awareness on the need for family friendly practices. It is recommended to continue to promote family friendly practices among employers through direct and candid communication between employers and employees. Thus, a family friendly employment culture must be cultivated. Besides encouragement, it is also recommended that effective means in implementing FFEPs according to different industries i.e. business environments and operations must be developed. Good practices or guidelines are advised to be consolidated to share among different sectors.

On awareness of family-related programs, the promotion of intergenerational activities to strengthen family structures and intergenerational harmony as well as the involvement of more young people in family-related programs is recommended

For future of family surveys and studies, the findings of the Family Surveys 2015 provide useful information regarding people's attitude and behavior related to family and work. It is recommended that the Family Survey should be conducted periodically. It is also worthy to explore how FFEPs can help address the difficulties experienced by parents at work in balancing work and family. More specifically, it will be advisable to explore the impact of five-day week on family life satisfaction, parental stress as well as parent-child and grandparent-grandchild relationship.

Family-school relationships survey of Panorama Education collaborates with school districts and state departments of education to design and implement survey programs for students, parents, and teachers. Panorama offers a technology platform to support survey administration and create reports that are clear, actionable, and, most importantly help teachers and administrators improve their schools. Panorama's client services team helps districts and states implement survey programs in line with best practices. Panorama currently runs survey programs in over 6,000 schools in 35 states, including those in the Connecticut State Department of Education, San Francisco United School District, and Teach for America

Family engagement is no longer viewed as a one-way street. Family-school relationships are still about how schools can more effectively engage parents and guardians. But developing parents' capacity to contribute to their children's learning is just as important. This approach to thinking about family school dynamics requires understanding these relationships as partnerships between groups of stakeholders invested in student success. The first step towards building these partnerships is to measure parent and families' attitudes and perceptions about their ties to their children's schools. The Family-School Relationships Survey was developed to provide schools with a clear picture of family attitudes about an array of topics. The survey covers topics like parent engagement, parent support, school climate, and parent efficacy. The survey helps schools assess their strengths and areas for improvement in a number of key areas.

The Business Mirror Editorial (2017) article entitled “Strengthening Filipino Families” believes that not too many Filipinos might be aware that there is such a thing as a National Family Week held every fourth week of September, and that the country just concluded its 25th-year celebration of the event. The National Family Week is based on the Presidential Proclamation 60 by former President Fidel V. Ramos signed in September 22, 1992. It aims at strengthening family unity and relationships through the promotion of Filipino family values. The Department of Social Welfare and Development serves as chair of the National Committee on the Filipino Family, together with partners from other government agencies, non-governmental organizations, academe, churches and socio-civic groups. Last year’s theme was “Tungo sa Maginhawaj Matatag at Panatag na Pamilyang Pilipinoj” which envisions better initiatives to strengthen the Filipino family in the new generation. The Family Code states that “the family is the foundation of our nation.” But what constitutes a family nowadays? Family relations are no longer confined between husband and wife or parents and children, or among brothers and sisters, as defined in the Family Code. Today, millions of Filipinos work abroad, where more women join the work force every day and where there are more dual-income families than ever before. It is not uncommon to have married couples or parents and children who live in different places, to have grandparents caring for grandchildren or aunts and uncles caring for nieces or nephews while the parents work overseas or other kinds of family structures. To visualize this perception, consider the following illustration:

Carlson et al. (2008) examined the relationship between subordinates’ family to work balance (conflict and enrichment) and two dimensions of contextual performance (interpersonal facilitation and job dedication) reported by supervisors. Beyond the direct effects they hypothesized that supervisor’s appraisals of employee conflict and enrichment would influence the supervisor’s contextual performance ratings. Data collected from a matched sample of 156 private sector employees and their supervisors indicated that the supervisor’s performance ratings were impacted by the supervisor’s appraisal of enrichment. However the supervisor’s appraisal of conflict only mattered for interpersonal facilitation. There was a direct effect of subordinate’s conflict on both dimensions of contextual performances.

Taylor, R. D. and Wang M. eds. (2012) with their study entitled “Resilience Across Contexts Family Work Culture and Community” focused on a number of societal risks that pose serious challenges to families’ well-being, many of which cut across divisions of class and race. According to them, these challenges include changes in the labor market and economy; the increasing participation of mothers in the laborforce; the changing nature of family structure and the composition of households; and the increase in the number of immigrant families. They believe that key institutions in the lives of families, like places of employment and schools, can play a significant role in fostering families’ capacity to adapt to the potential challenges they face. The authors’ research focuses on emerging issues that have significant implications for policy and practice in such areas as employment and new technologies; maternal employment and family development; family structure and family life; immigration, migration, acculturation, and education of children and youth; and social and human services delivery. The goal is to take stock of what is known from research and practice on some of the challenges facing children and families for policy development and improvement of practices.

Clark (2001) in his study “Work/Family Border Theory: A New Theory of Work/Family Balance” introduces work/family border theory - a new theory about work/family balance. According to the theory, people are daily border-crossers between the domains of work and family. The theory addresses how domain integration and segmentation, border creation and management, border-crosser participation, and relationships between border-crossers and others at work and home influence work/family balance.

Greenhaus and Allen (2011) with their study “Work-family balance: A review and extension of the literature” provide an updated review of the literature focusing on the negative and the positive aspects of combining work and family roles. Their goal is to explicate the concept of work-family balance. Specifically, they review alternative meanings of work-family balance found in the literature. They also offer definition of work-family balance and provide a tentative model. Moreover, they present suggestions for future research designed to clarify the meaning, uniqueness, antecedents, and consequences of work-family balance.

Aryee and Tan et al. (2005) with their study “Rhythms of Life: Antecedents and Outcomes of Work-Family Balance in Employed Parents” examined antecedents and outcomes of a fourfold taxonomy of work-family balance in terms of the direction of influence (work-family vs. family-work) and type of effect (conflict vs. facilitation). The respondents of the study were full-time employed parents in India. Results of moderated regression analysis revealed that different processes underlie the conflict and facilitation components. Furthermore, gender had only a limited moderating influence on the

relationships between the antecedents and the components of work-family balance. Last, work-family facilitation was related to the work outcomes of job satisfaction and organizational commitment. To have a safe, stable and supportive home environment have positive, trusted relationships with other people feel safe, secure and protected at home and in the community have a voice and the ability to raise concerns and have these concerns addressed feel valued and respected. Having material basics means that children and young people: have access to adequate, stable housing have access to adequate clothing and footwear have access to nutritious food and clean water have access to materials to support participation in activities have access to education and training materials have access to adequate heating and cooling Being healthy means that children and young people: are mentally and physically healthy have access to appropriate health and care services are emotionally well, happy and supported are immunised are as physically active as they can be Learning Participating Having a positive sense of culture and identity Learning means children and young people: are attending and engaging in education, training or employment are supported to learn by their caregiver and education providers are participating in early childhood education receive assistance for additional needs are developing literacy and numeracy skills appropriate to age Participating means children and young people: are engaging with peers and community groups are an active participant in their own life; including being able to have a say and have their opinion heard and valued are taking part in organised activities, including sport have access to and use technology and social media Having a positive sense of culture and identity means children and young people: can find out about family and personal history and are supported to connect positively with their culture have a positive sense of self-identity and self-esteem feel like they belong are in touch with cultural or spiritual practices and have these practices valued and respected.

Synthesis

It can be gleaned from the above related literature and related studies that the study definitely featured striking similarities and differences with previous studies. However, in the current study, focus on intergenerational relationships found in the family has been put into place as a very influential factor that contribute to the attainment of academic well-being among respondents as well as manifestation of love in the family. Tim and Ellie Brubaker (1999) study posited the “Four Rs” of respect, responsibility, reciprocity and resilience as part and parcel of the perpetuation of intergenerational relationships. Similarly, in the current study, it surfaced that while IR is positively and directly correlated with academic well-being, which says, the higher the IR, the stronger the academic well-being. Further, academic well-being is not after all automatic as such is continually sustained addressed in the various intergenerational relationships formed in the family. Uniquely, responsibility became the underpinning stamp of the presence of balance in the IR which sustains academic well-being among the 302 respondents.

CHAPTER III

Research Design and Methodology

Research Design

This study used both qualitative and quantitative approaches, specifically the descriptive - comparative design to describe the love in the family as manifested in the quality of intergenerational experienced by sophomore teacher education, civil engineering, nursing and accountancy students along the four Rs of respect, responsibility, reciprocity and resiliency and establish correlation. In addition, it also explored the significant relationship between the respondents' quality of IR and level of academic well-being. Personal experiences and challenges were as well determined and surfaced from the open ended questions imbedded in the survey checklist. These were culled and further discussed in interspersed manner to validate the qualitative data. It also used the focus group discussion to validate and enhance the data.

Research Locale

The study was conducted at Saint Mary's University, a premier school in the region, and a Catholic University nestled in the province of Nueva Vizcaya and municipality of Bayombong. A CICM school offering basic education and different programs of discipline in the tertiary level under the leadership of the first lady President Dr. John Octavious S. Palina for school year 2019-2020.

Research Respondents

This study was carried out in the tertiary level among 302 respondents - specifically the first batch of the k to 12 curriculum sophomore students across the four schools, the selected respondents of Saint Mary's University Bayombong Nueva Vizcaya. Selected representatives from the banner program such as BSED/BEED, BSCE, BSA and BSN were taken into priority as most of them were the products of the more intricate and demanding fields of specialization where very strong level of experiences of intergenerational relationships and possibly be the arena for the development of academic well-being. Sophomore living with parents, with siblings, with older siblings and living with grandparents are the focal respondents of the proposed study. The freshmen from the k to 12 were reserved for the pilot test of the tool. Since there are fewer sophomore students across the different area of discipline sampling with 75% of the designated class was followed

Research Instruments

Survey checklist on the Four Rs of respect, responsibility, reciprocity by Timothy Brubaker and Ellie Brubaker(1999) was adopted with contextualized open-ended questions to be crafted by the researchers. It is a questionnaire to answered by 302 respondents with Very Weak:1, Weak:2, Strong:3 and Very Strong:4.

The current study has been accomplished through a validated survey checklist adopted from Survey Questionnaire on the Four Rs of respect, responsibility, reciprocity by Timothy Brubaker and Ellie Brubaker (1999) was substantiated with contextualized open-ended questions to be crafted by the researchers. It is a questionnaire answered by 302 respondents with Very Weak:1, Weak:2, Strong:3 and Very Strong:4. on the four Rs of intergenerational relationships among sophomore students who are known to be the first batch of the k to 12 curriculum as to date. Banner programs in the different schools were intentionally chosen as the respondents.

The Psychometric properties of the tool that was used has been further evaluated and critiqued by psychometrician and statistician in accordance to the problems of the study prior to its production.

Data Gathering Procedure

The following process were followed to gather relevant data.

1. After the evaluation, deliberation and approval of the committee of the proposed study, the instrument was adopted, contextualized and validated among freshmen students who were not the direct respondents but already included in the k to 12 curriculum.
2. Production of the survey checklist was done prior to the floating.
3. The survey checklist was personally administered to the 302 respondents, sophomore teacher education (34), accountancy (112), nursing (104) and civil engineering (52) students, sampling of the population of each program was followed.
4. Scheduled focus group discussion and interview was conducted for each program to validate data.
5. The data gathered from the 302 respondents were encoded and subjected to SPPSS

v. 10

Treatment of Data

1 and 2. The quality of intergenerational relationship with the four Rs and academic well-being was determined following the Likert scale:

Quality of Intergenerational Relationship in the Family and Academic Well-being

1	VERY WEAK	Means to a very little extent (1.0-1.49)
2	WEAK	Means to a little extent (1.5-2.49)
3	STRONG	Means to a modest extent (2.5-3.49)
4	VERY STRONG	Means to a great extent (3.5-4.00)

3. Significant relationship between the respondents' quality of IR and level of academic well-being was noted and obtained from the mean scores based on the research instrument after the analysis and interpretation

4. Experiences on the IR in the family by the sophomore students that affect their academic well-being were culled and interspersed with the discussions in Chapter IV. Various challenges they are immersed to in achieving academic well-being in their life were put down into writing and documented together with the experiences.

5. Interventions were provided based on the results and laid down by the researchers to enhance existing program on shepherding and mentoring.

CHAPTER IV

Results and Discussion

The table below presents the total number of respondents, 302. Evidently, the accountancy students topped with the total of 112 followed by the nursing students with a total of 104. The civil engineering students ranked third with 52 respondents. Finally, the teacher education had the lowest number of respondents of 32 as expected, enrollees of this program in various HEIs suffered drastic decrease among others.

Section 1: Quality of intergenerational relationships along the 4Rs

Table 1DZ Respondents' Program and Condition

Course	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
BSED/BEED	34	11.26	11.26	11.26
BSCE	52	17.22	17.22	28.48
BSA	112	37.09	37.09	65.56
BSN	104	34.44	34.44	100.00
TOTAL	302	100.00	100.00	

Among the 302 respondents, there were 215 females who dominated the group and 87 males coming from the four schools. Interestingly, 227 are living with their parents and siblings; 53 are living with their parents only ; 14 are living with their parents and grandparents; 3 are independently living, and 5 are living with their grandparents as main support.

Table 2: Living structure and Sex of Student Respondents

Living with parents	53
Living with parents and older siblings	227
Living with parents and grandparents	14
Living independently	3
Living with grandparents	5
TOTAL	302

Sex	Frequency	Percent
Male	87	28.81
Female	215	71.19
TOTAL	302	100.00

The quality of the intergenerational relationships across the four Rs has been further explored with 10 item statements reflective of the respect, responsibility, resilience and reciprocity experienced by the various respondents.

The table below shows that in terms of the quality of respect which is a crucial component in maintaining relationships within the family, the mean score derived was 3.46 which is qualified as strong. It can be noted that items 1 to 6 were rated very strong simply because these items were deeply felt and experienced by the students. As many of the respondents vividly wrotej "my parents, even my grandparents and siblings accepted me for what I am and I feel this at home". More extensively as noted further in their experiences and challenges, many of the students revealed that they give due respect to their parents and grandparents as they follow what they like them to fulfill specifically on

matters related to studies. Items 7 to 10 were however rated strong though the difference is not quite significant as the items were all rated strong. Both items 1 and

2 “ I experience respect and acceptance from my parents, older siblings and grandparents and I manifest respect in my dealing to everyone at home “ were rated 3.75 which is very strong. As reflected in the ratings, these were seen of high quality as such were strongly encountered and experienced by the various students.

Further however, only item number 8 which says “I am emotionally stable opening up to my parents, older sibling and grandparents” was rated with a mean score of 2.66. This probably portray the struggle of the sophomore students then to connect openly with the various members of the family as many students may not have this as their first option with the assumption that they are not emotionally stable.

The over-all mean score is 3.46 along respect, this proves that most of the students have experienced this component of intergenerational relationship strongly as a paramount aspect of building relationships in the family across different ages.

Table 3: Quality of Intergenerational Relationships

Respect

RESPECT	Mean	Std. Deviation	Qualitative Descriptor
1. I experience respect and acceptance from my parents, older siblings and grandparents.	3.75	0.53	Very Strong
2. I manifest respect in my dealings to everyone at home.	3.75	0.48	Very Strong
3. I can closely relate with my parents as I am respected of who I am	3.63	0.65	Very Strong
4. I am fully accepted and valued with my own personhood at home.	3.70	0.58	Very Strong
5. I enjoy the company of everyone home as there is equity.	3.57	0.65	Very Strong
6. I am highly regarded with my dignity by everyone at home .	3.62	0.61	Very Strong
7. I am not hostile keeping in touch to everyone at home.	3.07	0.83	Strong
8. I am emotionally stable opening up to my parents, older siblings an grandparents.	2.66	0.93	Strong
9. I feel belongingness at home where I experience recognition of my strengths and understanding of my weaknesses.	3.42	0.74	Strong
10. I have a voice and the ability to raise concerns and have these concerns addressed as I feel loved, valued and respected.	3.39	0.72	Strong
Mean Respect	3.46	0.48	Strong

It could be gleaned from the table found on the next page that responsibility -which is considered as another component reshaping the existence of intergenerational relationships has been revealingly rated with the mean score of 3. 52 among others. This gives the picture that the element of responsibility is so much embedded in the experience of intergenerational relationship. Indeed, one may not discount this underpinning stamp for a relationship to be in tack as most of the members were young or old are

practically cognizant of their existing responsibilities. The parents for instance as insinuated by most of the respondents are seen supportive of their studies and needs as they find these as their prime role. Students on the other hand are also fully aware of their tasks and responsibilities to finish their studies.

Evidently, seven items were rated very strong. There were only 3 items namely: I have the ability to respond in any circumstance at home; I feel valued performing my duty at home and I share goals and objectives at home “. This proves however that the over-all mean score of 3.52 very strongly captures the immanence of the value of respect in sustaining intergenerational relationships. Hence. Every member is a potent contributor and performer of a certain goal and objective which the family likes to accomplish. As many respondents mentioned” our parents take the responsibility by all means to send us to school to finish our studies...it is also now our responsibility to study harder”.

**Table 4: Quality of Intergenerational Relationships
Responsibility**

RESPONSIBILITY	Mean	Std. Deviation	Qualitative Descriptor
1 . I have a safe, stable and supportive home environment with everyone in the family.	3.68	0.55	Very Strong
2. I have the ability to respond in any circumstance at home.	3.43	0.62	Strong
3. I feel valued performing my duty at home.	3.44	0.66	Strong
4. I am willing to perform my duties and obligation at home .	3.57	0.60	Very Strong
5. I have positive sense of culture and identity.	3.58	0.59	Very Strong
6. I experience equity in term of rights and privileges.	3.50	0.60	Very Strong
7. I accomplish my tasks and assignments as a child and a student without being forced.	3.5	0.64	Very Strong
8. I am treated kindly and nicely as a person by everyone as there is shared responsibility.	3.60	0.55	Very Strong
9. I can relate positively with others in accomplishing my responsibilities like giving care and support to everyone .	3.55	0.56	Very Strong
10. I share common goals and objectives with everyone at home .	3.37	0.71	Strong
Mean Responsibility	3.52	0.46	Very Strong

Table 5 below presents another component of intergenerational relationship which is reciprocity. As revealed from the results, this was rated with a mean score of 3.48 which is similar with respect and resilience. Among the ten item statements on reciprocity, 7 were rated very strong. There were only 3 where were rated strong which are: I enjoin my grandparents with my day to day encounters; I am allowed to exercise autonomy in making my decisions and I do things reciprocally with everyone at home. This implies that give and take atmosphere of the intergenerational relationship is strongly felt among the students. Meaning connectivity and concern are mutually experienced. Thomas(2017) in his study on family relationships claimed that such institutions are enduring and consequential for academic well-being across the life course.

Table 5: Quality of Intergenerational Relationships

Reciprocity			
RECIPROCITY	Mean	Std. Deviation	Qualitative Descriptor
1. I experience reciprocal love with everyone at home	3.57	0.65	Very Strong
2. I am consistently keeping in touch with my parents , siblings and grandparents/	3.50	0.75	Very Strong
3. I feel sense of belongingness at home.	3.59	0.65	Very Strong
4. I experience harmony staying at home.	3.58	0.65	Very Strong
5. I am willing to take care and attend to concerns at home	3.66	0.54	Very Strong
6. I experience two -way attention at home.	3.42	0.69	Strong
7. I am inspired by my parents, older siblings and	3.70	0.59	Very
8. I enjoin my grandparents with my day to day	3.19	0.94	Strong
9. I am allowed exercise autonomy in making my	3.28	0.71	Strong
10. I do things for everyone reciprocally at home.	3.32	0.65	Strong
Mean Reciprocity	3.48	.48	Strong

The quality of the component on resilience on table 6 reveals that the over-all mean score of 3.49 is strong. Among the 4Rs this ranked the second which means that this is a paramount ingredient in the strong quality of intergenerational relationships among the various respondents. Conversely, while responsibility is seen as the underpinning stamp, such is complemented with the resilience shared by the different members in contending challenging family dynamics. Dominantly out the ten item experiences on resilience, six were rated strong and item 6 which says "I experience unwavering support and understanding at home" was rated the lowest mean score of 3.30. This surfaced as students somehow are wanting to have consistency of support and understanding provided at home.

Table 6: Quality of Intergenerational Relationships

Resilience			
RESILIENCE	Mean	Std. Deviation	Qualitative Descriptor
1. I find my family very supportive of me even in most difficult times.	3.60	0.65	Very Strong
2. I am assured of enduring love, support from everyone at home.	3.65	0.58	Very Strong
3. I experience solidarity at home even in the midst of challenges and untoward incidents.	3.46	0.67	Strong
4. I have strength hope and vigor to confront problems ahead.	3.39	0.71	Strong
5. I can withstand the test of time as I feel supported.	3.42	0.66	Strong
6. I have sense of courage shared with everyone in facing the challenges of life.	3.41	0.64	Strong
7. I have deep sense of trust accorded to my family and God in most challenging times	3.61	0.58	Very Strong
8. I experience unwavering support and understanding at home .	3.30	0.78	Strong
9. I am assured that my parents, older siblings and grandparents think about my academic well-being	3.57	0.66	Very Strong
10. I can manage strategies which are responsive to our needs at home especially during most difficult times.	3.47	0.57	Strong
Mean Resilience	3.49	0.47	Strong

Table 7 shows another way of surfacing the level of the 4RS of intergenerational relationships along four item statements - one each of the 4 RS. Significantly, it is revealed that the over-all mean 3.53 - quality of the 4Rs is very strong. Out of the four item conditions and experiences only the component of reciprocity was rated strong with the mean score of 3.46 which is the lowest among others. This can be affirmed with the experiences mentioned by students that at times reciprocity is in a great deal quite tough to be shown in so far as there are problems that impede them like they are not able to reach the expectations of their family members. Respect was rated the highest with the mean score of 3.59, very strong which when compared to the ten item experiences of the students, slight difference was noted as respect was rated only strong with the mean score of 3.46. This was followed by responsibility which was rated 3.58 and seen consistent with the rating derived from the ten item conditions with the mean score of 3.52. This shows that indeed responsibility is seen very pervasive on the relationships of the students as it becomes the underpinning stamp of the belongingness they have in the family. As mentioned by many students, they know that everyone else has to be responsible. Their being part of the family is notably sustained with the component of responsibility. The component on resilience however has been rated very strong with a mean score of 3.51 which is slightly higher with the ten item conditions which were rated 3.49 strong. From this one can surmise that the component of resilience is actually imbedded in intergenerational relationships. Nonetheless, its meaning and rating have been differently noted as students may have various experiences and may have different ways of actualizing such. Culturally even, resilience which is referred to as *katatagang-loob* in the Filipino context as mentioned by Tiangco (2017) may be an idea of strength (*tibay*) within the context of *matatag* or *katatagan* is characterized not as forceful strength or power but rather as a sense of stability, durability and endurance. The respondents have as well regarded this as attribute of their parents or grandparents. As one expressed during the focus group discussion” I do not have my parents with me as they have they own families but my grandparents have been supporting me over the years. It does not make any difference somehow but this situation propelled me to be resilient and more motivated to study harder.” From this, it surfaced that resilience is inherent trait or characteristic of the various members of intergenerational relationships.

Table 7: Over-all Quality on the 4RS of Intergenerational Relationships

OVER-ALL QUALITY ON THE 4RS OF INTERGENERATIONAL RELATIONSHIPS	Mean	Std. Deviation	Qualitative Descriptor
1. I experience respect that is deeply imbedded in all my intergenerational relationships at home.	3.59	0.59	Very Strong
2. I feel sense of responsibility in sustaining my family.	3.58	0.58	Very Strong
3. I manifest reciprocity in my dealings to my parents, older children, grandparents and sibling	3.46	0.66	Strong
4. I find resilience in the family as shown by my parents, older children, grandparents and siblings especially during difficult times.	3.51	0.66	Very Strong
Mean Over-all Quality	3.53	0.53	Very Strong

Table 7 extends however another findings that with the 4 item over-all quality, the mean score derived was 3.53, very strong which when compared with the 10 item experiences on the 4 Rs strong mean score 3.49 was only derived. Hence, thus summing up, mean score of 3.49.

Section 2: Academic well-being

Table 8 below presents the level of academic well-being experienced by the different respondents who came from the major programs offered by the different schools namely, civil engineering, nursing, accountancy and teacher education.

Table 8: Academic Well-being

ACADEMIC WELL BEING	Mean	Std. Deviation	Qualitative Descriptor
1. I experience vigor and inspiration to accomplish my tasks and responsibilities as a student.	3.51	0.64	Very Strong
2. I feel engaged with all the undertakings I have in school.	3.25	0.68	Strong
3. I experience balance between my academic life and intergenerational relationships.	3.13	0.72	Strong
4. I am bursting with energy when I am doing my work academically.	2.96	0.74	Strong
5. I am enthusiastic about my studies as I get full support at home and in school.	3.28	0.69	Strong
6. I am happy relating with others in school.	3.28	0.68	Strong
7. I am capable of doing more complicated assignments in class if I try hard enough.	3.23	0.69	Strong
8. I feel emotionally drained and exhausted with my studies.	3.05	0.88	Strong
9 I doubt the significance of my studies.	2.40	0.89	Weak
10. I feel happy embracing the four pillars of education such as learning to know, learning to do, learning to relate with others and learning to be.	3.49	0.66	Strong
Mean Academic Well Being	3.16	0.44	Strong

Among the ten item experiences and conditions of academic well-being, nine were rated strong. Item number 1 which is “ I experience vigor and inspiration to accomplish my tasks and responsibilities as a student “ was the only one rated with mean score of 3.51, very strong. This affirms that all the respondents are fully aware that academic well-being starts with their own investment of their own potentialities, willingness, interest to accomplish their tasks and responsibilities with high spirit and interest. As revealed by many students, “ I like to accomplish my tasks”. Understandably, item 9 which says “ I doubt the significance of my studies” was the only one rated with a mean score of 2.40 qualified as weak. This proves that the respondents are fully aware of their purpose in going to school. Their academic well-being is paramount in so far as this is dependent with the expectations and support they derive from their intergenerational relationships.

Item 4 which says “ I am bursting with energy when I am doing my work academically” was rated the second lowest. This tells that the students may be fully aware of their academic assignments but the energy may not be enough to sustain or respond to all the tasks they are expected to. As noted from their experiences and challenges, many students lack the drive at times to respond to their academic work with urgency. Many of them mentioned “laziness and lack of focus are my challenges” as well as “some teachers are not inspiring”.

Significantly, item number 10 which says “ I feel happy embracing the four pillars of education such as learning to know, learning to do, learning to relate with other and learning to be “ was rated the second highest. This confirms that the students’ academic well -being is directly attributed to their experience of the four pillars of education which one cannot discount. Moreover, since the respondents are the first batch of the k to 12 curriculum, their learning experiences which contribute to their academic well-being is advanced and diversified as they are attuned to completing their performance tasks. It is also noted that part and parcel of their well-being is the value of happiness attached to their academic life. Items 5 and 6 which says : “ I am enthusiastic about my studies as I get full support at home and in school “ and “ I am happy relating with others in school” were both rated with a mean score of 3. 28, strong. As revealed from the results, academic well-being of the respondents are indeed fostered through the support experienced not only at home but also in school. At the same time, this is fostered with the capability and happiness of the students in the other relationships they have in school with their teachers and classmates. The item “I feel emotionally drained and exhausted with my studies” was as well rated 3. 05, strong. This shows that part and parcel of academic well- being is the presence of lightness and positive energy. Students somehow find the stress of going to school most especially when they are emotionally drained and exhausted probably because of the many demands of the new curriculum. A one student mentioned “My clinical instructor degraded me”. This proves that emotional stress many not

just be contributed with the bulk of academics given per program but with the kind of treatment experienced from teachers.

The over-all mean score for academic well-being is strong with the rating of 3.16. This describes the fact that among the various respondents, academic well-being which is experienced in various ways may be supported with the items on "I experience balance between my academic life and interpersonal relationships" which was rated with a mean score of 3.13 together with "I feel engaged with the undertakings at home" rated with a mean score of 3.25. Evidently, from these experiences which are qualified as strong, one can get the picture that indeed the level of academic well-being is never detached with the balance that is derived between the presence of intergenerational relationships where the respondent feel being loved and at the same time supported. Tim and Ellie Brubaker (1999) affirmed that the occurrence of the "The Four Rs" of respect, responsibility, reciprocity and resilience are very relevant to all forms of families and to persons who work with older people and their families. These qualities can be foundations for bolstering and strengthening intergenerational bonds, can undergird professional practice and can be potent factors for the students to achieve academic well-being. There are parameters that would measure academic well-being among students. For students who are after excellent performance, theirs is contentment, should they achieve their goals. Too much engagement with their studies without being disturbed by outside factors and familial problems can be considered. Brown and Mitchell (1991) defined performance obstacles as factors in any environment that restrict the optimum productivity. It can be noted that in recent years, several definitions on academic well-being have mushroomed which have become paramount (Ben-Arieh and Frones, 2011). While it is true that a framework can guide the development of quality academic well-being, it may generally leave the impression that anyone who is subjected to any educational activity is someone who feels happy, contented and unafraid to go to school because of the feeling of the existence of readiness.

Section 3: Significant relationship between the respondents' quality of intergenerational relationships and level of academic well-being

Table 9. Significant relationship between the respondents' quality of intergenerational relationships and academic well-being

Quality of Intergenerational Relationships		N=302 Academic Well-being
RESPECT (3.46)	Pearson Correlation	.549**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	Decision	Reject HO
RESPONSIBILITY(3.52)	Pearson Correlation	.600**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	Decision	Reject HO
RECIPROCITY(3.48)	Pearson Correlation	.550**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	Decision	Reject HO
RESILIENCE(3.49)	Pearson Correlation	.590**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	Decision	Reject HO
OVER-ALL(3.53)	Pearson Correlation	.637**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	Decision	Reject HO

Having noted the ratings derived and culled from the results presented on Table 9, it is very evident and consistent that there is significant relationship at 0.01 on the respondents' quality of intergenerational relationships along the 4Rs and level of academic well-being. They are positively or directly correlated with one another. This reveals that the higher the quality of the four Rs, the higher or the stronger the quality of academic well-being. Significantly, the quality of experiences of the intergenerational relationships along the four Rs is rated very strong with the mean score of 3.49 along the 10 item experiences and 3.53 mean score with the over-all item which when added, yields 3.51 which is of very strong quality. In relation to academic well-being, data reveals that the mean score of 3.16, has been derived with strong quality. Significant relationship is seen as one could track down that the higher rating is derived from the quality of academic well-being, the quality of intergenerational relationships along the 4 Rs is evidently much higher which is very strong. This gives the picture that the 302 respondents are indeed in the context of loving and supportive network of intergenerational relationships that motivate them to study harder and attain academic well-being regardless of the many challenges and unprecedented conditions of being part of a family whether nuclear or extended where relationships are built from young to old. While one can notice that the mean score of the quality of intergenerational relationships experienced by these respondents is higher than academic well-being, one can derive the premise that the family which is the very root of their being definitely supports and influences the strong academic well-being they have fostered.

Evidently, the respondents have surfaced the importance of the presence of the 4Rs in the various intergenerational relationships that they are into. Regardless of whether they live with their parents, grandparents and older siblings - complete or not, the kind of support they get may have great influence in their academic well-being. As many of the respondents mentioned "I study because my parents and grandparents are expecting much from me and I find it as a responsibility". In fact among the 4Rs, responsibility has been rated the highest hence thus considered as the underpinning component of sustained intergenerational relationships.

Section 4: Experiences and Challenges on intergenerational relationships in the family by the sophomore students that influence or affect their academic well-being

The various respondents who are the first batch of the k to 12 curriculum from the four banner programs of the different schools namely teacher education, civil engineering, nursing and accountancy mentioned several experiences and challenges they have been immersed into over the years. As learners coming from diverse familial dynamics, structures such as the presence and absence of intergenerational relationships, striking commonalities and struggles were surfaced.

As reflected in the results of the survey questionnaire that was given to the 302 respondents, it was made clear that their experiences of intergenerational relationships among the 4Rs have been topped with the component of responsibility with the mean score of 3.52. This was followed by resilience with the mean score of 3.49; reciprocity, 3.48 and respect, 3.46. All of these are definitely mirrored in their narratives and revelations of their unique experiences and tough challenges they gone through over the years. The discussion of these experiences and challenges 4Rs follow the highest mean rating to the lowest.

A. Responsibility

Based from the results of the survey and validation through focus group discussion, it is noted that the existing landscape of the students' quality of intergenerational relationship has been built very strongly with the understanding of responsibility among the respondents. This component is deeply ingrained on them as many recognized the responsibility translated into action by their parents, grandparents and other people they keep in touch with. They know that while it is the responsibility of their parents and grandparents to support them, they too are held liable and responsible to fulfill their tasks as students.

Interestingly, the dominance of the component of responsibility served as the underpinning stamp of the intergenerational relationships experienced by the different respondents. Many of the respondents highlighted the support given to them by their families and enthused: "they are supportive in all my decisions, they just support me regardless if we have F.P; my family supports me all the way; my family's support financially and emotionally helps a lot in my studies. strong family support system inspires me to study harder and helps me do to more effort in my academics."

This implies that they truly experience the presence of supportive and very responsible parents as well as grandparents. In contrast however, for others, it has been a great advantage living with their parents but not for some as they find themselves all alone putting into their shoulder the myriad of responsibilities expected of them to accomplish because of the absence of their parents. As one sophomore student expressed, she was challenged paddling her own canoe by saying: **"The major problems that made me hard to adjust in my academic well-being is when my father died. I was emotionally challenged in which I was not able to focus on my academics... Also adding the fact of having a step father."** Similarly, another respondent mentioned **"the death of my parents, the responsibility of raising my own siblings as well as managing my home by myself"**. These actually mirror the consequences of not having any support from parents. Looking at this on a positive side however, the value of resilience and capability to embrace responsibilities out of one's volition is manifested though struggles and conflicts are at the same time experienced.

There are unlimited situations wherein the respondents experience the love through the support they receive from the various members in the family no matter what. One respondent confirmed that her parents are great motivators even during odd times as she said:

"My family motivates me whenever I feel down or suffering from an academic breakdown, they'll always say mahirap talaga pero isipin mo yung pangarap mo Inspirational messages each day and my parents sustain what I need and what I want"

Another respondent expressed:

"My family relationship keeps me strong and motivated despite the hardship in my studies because they always make sure that I am okay and they keep me on fighting for my future. "and "Seeing all the sacrifices of my family pushed me to study harder and achieve my best effort to make them proud".

Indeed, the experiences of the students are so much tied up with the value of shared responsibility. Most of the respondents recognized the unlimited support provided to specially to their studies. In the same manner, they also find the task of studying well as a positive response to their parents. The challenge to be able to finish their academics is seen crucial though as one engineering student mentioned: **"the strong influence of my parents towards my decisions in life that I will do the best in school for them. "** and **"living with your family can inspire you more to pursue your dreams."**

They too have their struggles but have realized that the intergenerational relationships they have made things easier amidst challenges, as one nursing student mentioned: "I am very open to my parents and since I am able to tell them everything, it is easier for me to cope with my problems and struggles." This implies that things try to go well with the help of older persons in the family. For several decades, research in gerontology and family studies has reported younger generations' feelings of responsibility for older generations who are their kin (Suitor, Pillemer, Keeton, & Robison, 1996). Filial responsibility defined as "a sense of personal obligation for the well-being of aging parents" (Hamon, 1996, p. 2), is felt by younger generations. At the same time, it was noted that parents are always there to provide everything especially when it comes to finances. Dominantly however, it was revealed from the respondents that financial concerns specially in paying tuition fees became the prevalent problem and challenge among others. Teacher education student said **"My family supports me financially and emotionally "; "my personal experience that influenced my academic well-being is seeing my family sacrificing to pay for my tuition fee "and "They support me financially but then I can feel the tension when I have failing grades"**.

From the experiences and challenges met by the students along responsibility, it is evident then that there is no family that discounts the support provided to students no matter what since they know very well that it is their responsibility to send their children to school. While there are difficulties in providing financial needs, there are other predicaments too that surface. Dominantly, many student mentioned laziness as the prime deterrent in accomplishing their responsibilities as students. Many students said: **" I get lazy sometimes and feel drawned that I don't want to study my notes sometimes and " I get lazy sometimes and feel exhausted in my studies"**.

B. Resilience

The component of resilience ranked as the second highest among the various 4Rs. This implies that this is deeply embedded in the character of the experiences of the different respondents. Indeed, this proved their capability to withstand everything ahead regardless of how difficult things are. Brubaker (1999) highlighted that this is one of the components of intergenerational relationships that holds the family together That even in most odd times and difficult challenges this somehow sustain the family. In the current study, it was surfaced that among students, trying times not only in terms of

finances but how they confront day to day encounters may be relegated to how they have experienced this at home with their parents, older siblings and grandparents. As one expressed **“ My family is Christ-centered....just like him...we try to be resilient with whatever is ahead of us”**. Moreover, this was attested by someone saying **“Moral support and financial support everytime I fell drained and exhausted with my studies they are there for me.”** Evidently one can draw the fact that the students are able to contend the challenges because of the support provided to them in the various intergenerational relationships that they have. Consistent prodding has been always there as someone mentioned:

“My family supported me on my chosen course even it is expensive course they are my family especially my parents are my inspirations in my studies, and they will always be the reason for not to give up no matter how hard life is”. Further, this was affirmed by someone **“My family relationship keeps me strong and motivated despite the hardship in my studies because they always make sure that I am okay and they keep me on fighting for my future.”** Further, one engineering students said: **“I am doing what my brother likes which is for me to become a civil engineer but I like to become an architect ”**. This implies that connectivity emanates not only with parents but even with older siblings to achieve and accomplish something.

The current study made evident that indeed, the strength of every student may be dependent with the support they receive back home. They are inspired to move on regardless of the difficulties that they encounter.

C. Reciprocity

The current study showed that the experiences of reciprocity in the various intergenerational relationships among the students are classified to be strong in nature. Hence thus two way traffic of support has been evidently encountered as they consistently connected with their parents, older siblings and grandparents as students perceived the relationship to be reciprocal. Sending them to school is responded by studying very well. As some respondents said: **“... parents are supportive so we reciprocate this by studying harder .”** Further, some also amplified the influence of their grandparents over the years as partners of their parent in giving support by saying: **“All my grandfathers and grandmothers are dead but we always make sure that we remember them.”**

Like any other relationship, throughout most of life, intergenerational relationships are characterized by reciprocity. The arrangement is two-way in nature. While younger generations support older relatives, older relatives are assisting younger persons. In short, intergenerational relationships in the later years are a two-way street. The classic example that many people readily observe is the child care provided by many grandparents and the emotional support adult children and grandchildren give to the grandparents. This was affirmed in the current study as one teacher education revealed that throughout, her parents allowed her to stay with her grandparents.

Even in intense caregiving situations, reciprocal relationships exist. Parents tell their adult caregivers that they love and appreciate them, and such emotional reinforcement can ease the burden of caregiving. Burton (1992) reported that in urban African American contexts, grandmothers sacrificed to provide care for their grandchildren and they received love and attention from their grandchildren. Similarly in the Philippine context and as revealed from the results of the study, grandparents are the partners if not the sole movers and motivators of many students in going to school and in the provision of many needs back home and school. One respondent from the school of engineering also mentioned: **“I’m inspired by their support and sacrifices which push me to do well in my studies.”** This was further confirmed by another respondent who highlighted the evident support given hence it is crucial to study harder to reciprocate the goodness of his parents by saying: **“When my parents especially my mom talked about her experiences at work. Through their support, I am inspired to do well despite the fact that I lack energy sometimes”**. Similarly agreed by another respondent who said: **It’s when my lola saying to me that I will become a Civil Engineer someday, they always motivate.** Further, another student explicitly recognized the assistance of grandparents by telling: **“My grandfather and grandmother are far away from us but they have great impact on my academic well-being. “I enjoy every companionship of my family specially my grandparent but they are now gone.”**

This component of the intergenerational relationship also posed some challenges among the students simply because they would like to give what is expected of them as students. Since they are supported emotionally and financially, they too find it like and obligation to reciprocate. On a positive light however, this opens avenues for realization as one student mentioned: **“Seeing all the sacrifices of my family pushed me to study harder and achieve my best effort to make them proud”**. This was

qualified further with the statement: " **Seeing all the sacrifices of my family pushed me to study harder and achieve my best effort to make them proud.**

D. Respect

Another important ingredient for intergenerational relationships to grow is the presence of respect in many ways. This could be both active and passive in nature. Interestingly, this has been rated to be strong though the lowest in rank among the 4Rs. In the various experiences of the students, it was revealed that this emanates freely not only with their parent but also to their older sibling and grandparents. As one student mentioned : " **Helping one another, cooperating and applying respect to others**" and " **I feel respected and trusted as I take every decision in my life. My parents and family are all supportive**". Similarly, someone also mentioned: " **support, acceptance and love from the family**". Evidently, these expressions are all directed to the manifestation of respect in the various intergenerational relationships. The students are indeed immersed in a respectful atmosphere when it comes to relationships in the family as they are allowed and accepted to be what they are.

Indeed, respect is a very important component that assures perpetuation of intergenerational relationships. The sophomore students who are part of younger generations evidence respect for older generations in numerous ways. As younger generations experience the usual benchmarks of maturation such as getting married, living independently, becoming parents, and developing a work pattern, relationships between the generations tend to become closer (Belsky & Rovine, 1984; Sutor & Pillemer, 1988; Roberts, Richards, & Bengtson, 1991). IN the case of the students however, this component is also challenged not only within the family but even in their academic well-being. Some students are compared for instance to other student which violates the recognition of human nature. Some parents somehow compare their children to their older siblings or to their classmates. This could be hurting as it disturbs the harmony found within the family. One student revealed: " **The most emotionally experienced was when I am being compared to anyone else that was the time I can't get through it because I was hurt.**" In addition, civil engineering student expressed: " **My father is very strict that sometimes I tend to lose motivation because sometimes he always expects more from me.**" Another accountancy student also mentioned: " **my parents are strict especially my father that sometimes I am already ashamed of myself because of what he is telling me about my grades and other activities**". Moreover, it is evident that understanding the dynamics of the various intergenerational relationship becomes complicated as one student mentioned the difficulty of respecting his father when he said " **My father's girlfriend disturbs my mom. She is jealous of my mom. I can't much time with my father when he got her.**"

It can be implied from the revelations of the students that their experience of respect is also manifested on the trust that they get from their parents . As one nursing student mentioned: " **My parents always doubt of my abilities they lack trust on me. They think that I'm wasting all their family money and efforts. They sometimes think that I'm lying**". Further, experiences in school also affect their idea of respect as one nursing student mentioned: " **Clinical instructor who degraded me.**"; **terror teachers who aren't even teaching well**" and accountancy student who revealed: " **I received so much hate from students, I don't even interact with . I am being judged and misunderstood by many.**

The value of respect is seen crucial as the students try to maximize everything they can which expects for acceptance not only to the different members in the family but more importantly in their academic well-being. Every student is unique who need care, support. Love, attention and respect. It is therefore paramount to give them more understanding as they are the first beneficiaries and experimental batch of k to 12 curriculum. As one student enthused " **because we are the first batch in K-12, we struggle with the new curriculum...we don't have a source we need to learn in our own**".

Indeed, all the 4Rs left indelible impact on the students' academic well-being. Several challenges have surfaced like acceptance of each person, capability to manage one's time, financial stability and ability to respond to any situation relevant to familial dynamics and academic concerns.

Section 5: Interventions to respond to the continuing search and attainment of academic well – being

As revealed on the current study, it was very evident that the quality of experiences of the respondents on the 4Rs of intergenerational relationships is **very strong** which influenced their academic well- being which was also rated **strong**. Interestingly while there is significance of the intergenerational relationships with the quality of academic well-being, there is a continuing response to still improve the

level of academic well-being. Hence thus, intervention activities are presented to enhance the existing services of the guidance office as well as the different learning activities in CFE 101 classes.

Rationale:

Intergenerational relationships are seen influential and enduring in attaining academic well-being. One may not discount its huge contribution in the life of an individual. It is paramount to provide an intervention that will track down and at the same time diagnose the existing conditions of which our students are immersed into. Hence, this enhancement program is geared to diagnose, monitor, and assist students in the 21st century and part of the K to 12 curriculum.

General Objectives:

1. To have extensive knowledge of the incoming freshmen vis a vis the 4Rs of intergenerational relationships and academic well-being
2. To provide intervention relevant to the attainment of academic well-being
3. To assist and help students cope with the situations they are immersed to as learners of the K to 12 curriculum and 21st century

Specific Objectives	Activity	Time Frame	Resource persons
1. To have in-depth profiling of the incoming freshmen	Getting to know the incoming freshmen through profiling <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interview • Survey Checklist on 4Rs of IR and Academic Well-being 	Before enrolment First Semester	Guidance Office and Testing Office CFE 101 teachers and other Teacher
2. To closely monitor students in their CFE 101 classes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Describing their Journey • Journal Writing • Classroom Based provision of the Survey Checklist on the 4RS of IR and Academic well-being 	First Semester	CFE101 teachers and research team
3. To provide seminar and for a on the 4Rs of IR and Academic Well-being	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Seminars and for a of various topics(Family, Intergenerational relationships, Academic Well-being, Time Management and Academic Counselling) 	First Semester	CFE 101teachers, Research team, Professional Education Department and Psychology Departmentt
4. To heighten monitoring to students with special concerns relevant to academic well-being and family support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal consultation 	Year round	Respective teachers in CFE 101, ProfEd and selected teachers
5. To collaborate with parents	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal consultation by appointment with parents 	Year round	Respective teachers in CFE 101, ProfEd and Selected teachers.

CHAPTER V

Summary, Conclusions and Recommendations

The current study revealed that there is a very strong quality of intergenerational relationships noted among the four components of responsibility, resilience, reciprocity and respect that significantly made relevant relationship with the students' academic well-being which was rated strong. It was derived that there is significant relationship of the quality of intergenerational relationship along the four Rs and academic well-being. Positive and direct correlation surfaced which tells that the higher the intergenerational relationships along the four Rs, the better the academic well-being.

1. The component of responsibility among others surfaced as the underpinning stamp for the sustained relationships of the students as well as their parents, older siblings and grandparents. Having noted the ratings derived and culled from the results it is very evident that the respondents' quality of intergenerational relationships and level of academic well-being are correlated with one another.

2. The academic well-being is strong among the various respondents.

3. The stronger the level of academic well-being, the quality of IR too has been rated very strong. Strikingly, the quality of experiences of the intergenerational relationships along the four Rs is rated very strong. In relation to academic well-being, data reveals that such is fostered by the kind of support received from the family very strongly anchored with responsibility.

4. Diversified challenges and experiences of intergenerational relationships and academic well-being emerged such as financial problems and laziness among others.

5. Intervention is necessary for the students hence, enhancement activities were crafted.

Uniquely, relationship is seen as one could tract down that the higher the rating is derived from the quality of academic well-being, the quality of intergenerational relationships along the 4 RS is evidently much higher which is qualified as very strong. It can be implied that the 302 respondents are indeed in the context of loving and supportive network of intergenerational relationships that motivate them to study harder and attain academic well-being regardless of the many challenges and unprecedented conditions of being part of a family whether nuclear or extended where relationships are built from young to old. While one can notice that the mean score of the quality of intergenerational relationships experienced by then respondents is higher than academic well-being, one can derive the premise that the family which is the very root of their being definitely supports and influences the strong academic well-being they have fostered.

Similarly, Thomas (2017) in his study on family relationships claimed that such institutions are enduring and consequential for academic well-being across the life course. What is significantly different is the nature of experiences and challenges surfaced since most of these mirrored their current situation as students being supported by intergenerational relationships.

Recommendations

1. The survey checklist should be provided to entering freshmen in collaboration with the existing program of the Guidance Office on Student Services.

2. The intervention program meant to enhance the existing program of the university shall be adopted not only to the cluster of the current study but across the different schools especially among freshmen who are part of the K to 12 curriculum.

3. The conduct of the survey checklist on the four Rs of intergenerational relationships and academic well-being should be followed in a classroom based monitoring to be initiated by the CFE 101 instructors and research team for deepened profiling.

4. The intervention program shall be a tandem task of the various departments namely Catholic Faith Education, Professional Education and Psychology Department specifically on the provision of seminars, trainings, fora and guidance and counselling activities.

5. The survey checklist can be used per school through the Dean's office to profile students for connectivity and more assistance.

References

- Brubaker H. & Brubaker E. (1999) The four Rs of Intergenerational Relationships: implications for practice. Volume 04, Issue 1, DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.3998/mfr.4919087.0004.102> NYUSA
- Briggs, R. (1998). *Caregiving daughters: Accepting the role of caregiver for elderly parents*. New York: Garland Publishing, Inc.
- Burton, L. M. (1992). Black grandparents rearing children of drug-addicted parents: Stressors, outcomes and social service needs. *Gerontologist, USA*
- Diller, J. V. (1999). *Cultural diversity: A primer for the human services*. Belmont, CA: Brooks/Cole.
- Hamon, R. R. (1996). Filial responsibility. In T. H. Brubaker (Ed.) *Visions 2000* (pp. 1-2). Minneapolis, MN: National Council on Family Relations.
- Gilligan M., Suito J. J., Feld S., & Pillemer K. (2015). Do positive feelings hurt? Disaggregating positive and negative components of intergenerational ambivalence. *Journal of Marriage and Family, 77*, 261-276. doi:10.1111/jomf.12146 USA
- Graham J. E., Christian L. M., & Kiecolt-Glaser J. K. (2006). Marriage, health, and immune function: A review of key findings and the role of depression. In Beach S. & Wamboldt M. (Eds.), *Relational processes in mental health*, Vol. 11. Arlington, VA: American Psychiatric Publishing, Inc.
- Grundy E. (2005). Reciprocity in relationships: Socio-economic and health influences on intergenerational exchanges between third age parents and their adult children in Great Britain. *The British Journal of Sociology, 56*, 233-255. doi:10.1111/j.1468-4446.2005.00057.x London
- Harcourt K. T., Adler-Baeder F., Erath S., & Pettit G. S. (2013). Examining family structure and half sibling influence on adolescent well-being. *Journal of Family Issues, USA*
- Harrington Meyer M. (2014). *Grandmothers at work - juggling families and jobs*. New York, NY: NYU Press.
- Hartwell S. W., & Benson P. R. (2007). Social integration: A conceptual overview and two case studies. In Avison
- W. R., McLeod J. D., & Pescosolido B. (Eds.), *Mental health, social mirror* (pp. 329-353). New York: Springer. Pawilen, G. (2018). *Social dimensions of Education*. Rex Bookstore. Recto, Manila .
-

APPENDIX 1: EXPERIENCES AND CHALLENGES

they are supportive in all my decisions
they just support me regardless if we have F.P.
the most emotionally experienced was when I am being compared to anyone else that the time I can't get through it because I was hurt
the personal experience I have in the family that influenced my academic well-being is about time management
When they are cheering on me when I am down at times My family is Christ-centered
It's good my family supports me all the way
My family's support financially and emotionally helps a lot in my studies My family supports me financially and emotionally
None, Since all of them are very supportive Discipline within ourselves
Seeing all the sacrifices of my family pushed me to study harder and achieve my best effort to make them proud
They support and how am I doing
The death of my parents, the responsibility of raising my siblings as well as managing my home by myself
My family gives me inspiration and motivation in my studies
My older sister graduated without failing grades
the support system I have
our parents are always right even though I don't like it
one personal experience is strong family support system, it helps me to do more efforts in my academics
the strong influence of my parents towards my decisions in life that I will do best in school for them
they help me to cope up with my studies
I feel respected and trusted as I take every decision in my life. My parents and family are all supportive
Love & support from my family
My relatives give moral support and encourage me to finish my studies pressure from aunts
Family support
I'm very open to my parents and since I am able to tell them everything, it's easier for me to cope with my problems and struggles
Helping one another, cooperation within the family and applying respect to others
They inspire me in my academic well-being
They support me at my best and give all the possible supports
I need to be an academic well-being so that I can help in the future
Having a family problem that is connected in having a fair one of the member
They always advise me to study well
My family motivates me whenever I feel down or suffering from an academic breakdown, they'll always say "mahirap talaga pero isipin mo yung pangarap mo"
Inspirational messages each day and my parents sustain what I need and what I want
not opening much from them because of my school schedule that I always go home late from school
Acceptance, support and love from family
My family and friends always support me in times of need which I appreciate a lot because my success is also their success
My brother wants me to become but my parents wants me to be an engineer while I want to become an architect
The love and support of my aunt and uncles
They support me in my course even though it is expensive
My personal experience that influenced my academic well-being is seeing my family sacrificing to pay my tuition fee
Support and love
Moral support
Their motivational speeches about college experiences I am not born with a silver spoon in my mouth
Their support as a family makes me study harder
Not being forced to study harder
I don't receive so much support from my parents morally and financially, but I chose to serve them as my inspiration to strive harder
They support me financially, but then I can feel the tension whenever I have failing grades
Living with your family can inspire you more to pursue your dreams.

The thought my father being a mechanical engineer makes me inspired and challenged to maintain my grades as I am also the eldest.

My family relationship keeps me strong and motivated despite the hardship in my studies because they always make sure that I am okay and they keep me on fighting for my future

The experiences with them help me build who I am, they serve as my guidance and my protectors

My father wasn't home for many years because he is a seaman

All my grandfathers and grandmothers are dead but we always make sure that we remember them

My father is very strict that sometimes I tend to lose motivation because sometimes he always expects more from me.

I'm inspired by their support and sacrifices. Which push me to do well in my studies

When my parents especially my mom talked about her experiences at work

Through their support, I am inspired to do well despite the fact that I lack energy sometimes my parents' respect accepts all my plans and decisions in my life

My personal experiences or intergenerational relationships in my family is they

always supported me what I want to do in my life by their guidance it helps me to understand what is the right way to walk in.

The experience I encountered from my family is when they inspire me on how they

become successful in life. They told me of what they've been through. They want me to do my best.

My mother's motivation

It's when my lola saying to me that I will become a Civil Engineer someday The always motivate me

My grandfather's and grandmothers are far away from us but they have a great impact on my academic well-being

My parents are strict especially my father that sometimes I am already ashamed of myself because of what he is telling me about my grades and other activities

Happiness, their safety

I don't have a good relationship with my father

My father attained such higher degree that I am expected to do the same

The major problems that made me hard to adjust in my academic well-being is when my father died. I was emotionally challenged in which I was not able to focus on my academics. Also adding the fact of having a step father.

I enjoy the companionship of every member of my family especially my grandparents but my grandparents are gone

My father's girlfriend disturbs my mom. She is jealous of my mom. I can't much time with my father when he got her

With the help of my uncle which is engineer, he helps me sometimes in my course he's giving advice and personal experiences in the field of engineering

Too much expectations which lead to pressure

Their support, parents supports me in my academic well-being though they are the ones pushed me to take engineering course. There are times when I wanted to quit because honestly I don't love what I do but on the other hand just have faith in my parents and just do my part as a child and student

I cannot say anything about my family, they are really supportive, lovable, caring and understanding family. And if ever I have a problem in my studies they comfort and saying that it's alright

They motivate and support me in all I do especially in terms of academics

My family inspires me and that's grewat help to influence my academic well-being

My personal experiences on intergenerational relationships in the family that influences my academic well-being is that they motivated me in my studies and help me to study well.

I often talk with my mother, sometimes with my siblings about my studies. We have the practice of dinner time is reporting time

Family gatherings of when eating together, my grandparents always give time to confront me about the things going on with my life

High expectations

misunderstanding and conflicts

I feel so loved and supported by my parents in different perspectives

Positive - the love and support of family influence my academic well-being

parents encourage me to study hard as a child from a family. Now I still study hard to achieve the best.

My parents are competitive that is why I am also competitive

I am well-supported by my family

They provide eme enough money to ba able to buy what I want

My mother is my alarm clock every morning
somehow it made me feel uneasy because of my anxiety
They are supportive, when I didn't understand something they can help me
I have a very close relationship with my family where I am not forced to do things but I assure that I have
the ability to do it without being told
I experience to be respected, loved, cared by the family members in which it
influences me to give them back that things by studying very well.
Whenever I am in need of financial aspect at school my parents will be very supportive
My parents always doubt of my abilities they lack trust on me. They think that I'm wasting all their
family money and efforts. They sometimes think that I'm lying support from the family as well as their
trust and faith that I will graduate influence my academic well-being positively
My family supports me with my academics
scolding me when I came home late at night
none
It's pleasant since it is making me realize of how I am well especially when it comes to academic
opportunities
Being open with them in terms of academics and they give more advices about deeds that makes me
inspire to study hard
My family supported me one my chosen course even it is expensive course
they are my family especially my parents are my inspirations in my studies, and they will always be the
reason for not to give up, no matter how hard life is.
When I decided to shift in the educ course, at first, they didn't allow me. I plead to them sp they have no
choice but to allow me
I feel loved and supported by everyone so even I'm nearing to give up. I'll never quit When it comes to
intergenerational relationships my parents always support me, they cheer me up and love me always
always with my mother because she always supports me and believe that I can. She is so proud everytime
I have achievements even if I failed she's just there to cheer me up even through chat but my father has a
very high expectations and standards on me., The support and lve give to me. They put me to be the best
that I can be and even
support me to take new ventures in me life
they did not force me and they don't have high expectations
It may be one factor where they do not start a conversation at home, merely asking how my day has been,
how well am I doing with my studies nad etc. another is the repetitive phrases where things that make
me want to not pursue my education. I guess that would have to be picnics and out of the town activities
because though that we are able to unwind. Thourgh unwinding, I can focus now on the academic well-
being, and as a result, I can say that family can really become who the person is It is great because I am
getting the support and love I need
My mother once told me to study well. She keeps on motivating me to fill the spaces in my mind and
heart with kindness and happiness. I am using their pieces of advise in my education
Moral support and financial support, everytime I feel drained and exhausted in my studies, I feel that
they're there for me.
They check my academic well-being from time to time
None
My mother and grandparents always tell me that I need to finish mt studies for me to have a better future
Well, the best experiences that positively influence my academic well-being brought my relationship in
the family is the continuous support in every possible way
especially financial concern
When I have achievement my parentsare so proud and they gave me some reward My personal
experience on intergrational relationship in the family influence my academic well-being by supporting
and encouraging me
I am motivated by my own family because they always support in everything that's what I treasured
them for a lot
My parents always support me in anything that can't affect my negatives
In terms of my academic well-being, I always have the support from my family and they always motivate
me whenever I feel academically down
They are all challenging me to do my best
My parents and my siblings who are the one influence me in my academic well-being to continue their
legacy

They often tell me their experiences in schooling and its importance in my life so I strive harder for them and for myself

In our family, the rest of them are teachers \

My family's love, care and attention. Also, their support and being a source of inspiration

I feel the full support and trust from my mother which benefits me and inspires me as a student to do my best and to keep going even if it is hard

It affects my academic well-being if one member of our family is unwell in terms of health conditions as well as conflict in idealism

supportive environment; caring home

They are able to help me in decision-making because they're more experienced than me. Also, sometimes my mother nags at me to use my facebook for her to see things in social media

They're always supporting me at all times and they never hesitate to help me to finish my studies

I feel their support on my academics but sometimes forcing me immediately to graduate

They support and motivate me to do better

I feel more assured that I am valued at least

the biggest struggle I faced is that, in our family im the only one who take BSCO and they are all in the field of medicine so I struggle engaging with them with the field I

pusure. Sometime I ask them but they didn't know so there is effect in my academic

I want to be the first Engineer in our family that's why I'm trying to be well in academic

My parents are very supportive when it comes to my decisions but I'm not with them when it comes to my personal problems and struggles in my studies

My family are always there for me regarding to my academics except my mother. I didn't feel that she is supporting me

None

they always support me and they always ask me if how was school

the well-being of my parent. One time my dad got sick and I am so worried but I continue to priorities my study but still I pray for my dad

It helps me on focusing on my academic well-being, they motivate me on how to be successful, they are pushing me to strive for greatness and of the younger generations

I am obliged to be a role model for them since they might be copying or be inspired by me

My family is very supportive when it comes to my academics. They will do whatever it takes to fulfill my needs

Lack of motivation from them which led me not to focus more on my academics

My mother is a bookkeeper on our church influenced me to choose the BSA track and continue it

None

not being trusted

They are all supporting me in all decisions I make in my academic well-being My mother and father always encourage me to study

I get support but sometimes I hear negative comments about me that makes me think I am not good of what I am now taking up

It is hard to do well academically when there is too much pressure for you to succeed. I don't do well with high expectations

Problems within the family

I want to finish my studies because my parents are very supportive They help me do my best through encouragement

Pressure, from parents and family

My parents taught me that education is the best thing I can have The support and understanding of my parents

I think that is by being supportive of my parents and my grandparents to me, and believing that I can surpass and achieve my goals

from being supportive even me have big gaps

We still manage to get along despite the age gaps we have

They supports me even at the lowest peak of my life as a student they expectations

I'm more inspired to do good academically as everyone at home supports me no matter what path I choose to go as long as it's for my well-being

my family, regardless of which generation they belong to, continues to support me in my academics and in any endeavor I choose to take

My mother inspires me in studying accounting despite of me trying to give up on my course

My family is very supportive when it comes to my academic well-being, they are always there in my achievements and become my support system

My family fully supports me in my chosen program

Sharing with them what happened thje whole day

I am procrastinating so much

Consistent awardee since kindergarten

I learn things that my parents experienced when they are young like me, they teach us lessons that can help us on what we are experiencing right now

My personal experience on intergenerational relationships in the family that influence my academic well-being is the pressure of the need to also be successful in life and my chosen course and career

My mother keeps on motivating me when I am down my mother tells me to study

It helps but sometimes it is also within students that we feel bad everytime when we did not do good enough to give back to the support that everyone gives

they have the sincerest love and support that they always assure me that no matter

what happens, they are proud of me and they will always be there to support me

I spoiled by love, care, support and attention from my whole family and it inspires me a lot

My family helps me to overcome my problems in terms of academic problems

supporting me on what I am going and giving me money for my studies

My mom had high grades when she was in school, I also aim to have them but not entirely the pressure gets to me

To have enough support from my family morally, financially and spiritually. I also have their trust

In times of having difficulties in acads, I will always call them

my family always tell me to never overuse myself in studying because health is

always the priority. They keep telling me that doing my best and giving me best shot is already enough

they support me in whatever path I take

my family are very supportive that is the only reason for me to continue studying

they support me with all my academic decisions and encourages me to do well

None

not being trusted

They are all supporting me in all decisions I make in my academic well-being Problems within the family

I want to finish my studies because my parents are very supportive They help me do my best through encouragement

Pressure, from parents and family

My parents taught me that education is the best thing I can have The support and understanding of my parents

I think that is by being supportive of my parents and my grandparents to me, and believing that I can surpass and achieve my goals

We still manage to get along despite the age gaps we have

They supports me even at the lowest peak of my life as a student they expectations

I'm more inspired to do good academically as everyone at home supports me no matter what path I choose to go as long as it's for my well-being

my family, regardless of which generation they belong to, continues to support me in my academics and in any endeavour I choose to take

My mother inspires me in studying accounting despite of me trying to give up on my course

My family is very supportive when it comes to my academic well-being, they are always there in my achievements and become my support system

My family fully supports me in my chosen program

Sharing with them what happened thje whole day

I am procrastinating so much

my mother tells me to study

It helps but sometimes it is also within students that we feel bad everytime when we did not do good enough to give back to the support that everyone gives

they have the sincerest love and support that they always assure me that no matter

what happens, they are proud of me and they will always be there to support me

I spoiled by love, care, support and attention from my whole family and it inspires me a lot

My family helps me to overcome my problems in terms of academic problems supporting me on what I am going and giving me money for my studies
My mom had high grades when she was in school, I also aim to have them but not entirely the pressure gets to me
To have enough support from my family morally, financially and spiritually. I also have their trust
In times of having difficulties in acads, I will always call them
always the priority. They keep telling me that doing my best and giving me best shot is already enough
My parents taught me that education is the best thing I can have The support and understanding of my parents
I think that is by being supportive of my parents and my grandparents to me, and believing that I can surpass and achieve my goals
We still manage to get along despite the age gaps we have
They supports me even at the lowest peak of my life as a student
I'm more inspired to do good academically as everyone at home supports me no matter what path I choose to go as long as it's for my well-being
my family, regardless of which generation they belong to, continues to support me in my academics and in any endeavour I choose to take
My mother inspires me in studying accounting despite of me trying to give up on my course
I want to finish my studies because my parents are very supportive They help me do my best through encouragement
Pressure, from parents and family
It helps but sometimes it is also within students that we feel bad everytime when we did not do good enough to give back to the support that everyone gives
they have the sincerest love and support that they always assure me that no matter what happens, they are proud of me and they will always be there to support me
I spoiled by love, care, support and attention from my whole family and it inspires me a lot
My family helps me to overcome my problems in terms of academic problems supporting me on what I am going and giving me money for my studies
My mom had high grades when she was in school, I also aim to have them but not entirely the pressure gets to me
To have enough support from my family morally, financially and spiritually. I also have their trust
financial mattersbecause it has a huge impact in me
The challenge in being a student is memorizing all the details to get the answer
Challenges like financial concerns and to much pressure
My family's support
Time is too short
sometimes, it's hard but keeping it up and to never quit
sometimes I feel the pressure and toxicity from my major subjects
I get lazy sometimes and feel drawined that I don't want to study my notes sometimes
I get lazy sometimes and feel exhausted in my studiesfinancial
when everything is a requirement, it must be submitted at the same time and much times is also needed to accomplish them.
peer pressure. Since all of my friends are in the Dean's lister. I am pressured to achieve more to keep up with their level
time management
Financial problems, self-doubt
The complex assignments and projects challenge me, making me want to push myself further
It was difficult to achieve 90 GWA self-confidence
disappointing them
High Expectations
time management sometimes, I have difficulties doing my projects
doubt, self-confidence, stress, weaknesses Financial Difficulties
Too much work overload peer pressure
The financial needs for my studies Self-expectations
Sometimes I feel lazy to do homework's
Everything is overwhelming especially I'm about to graduate. Being strong
stress, allowance and financial needs

Being patient, because I wanted to work already Being away from home
Being emotionally and physically tired in doing things at home
Pressure
Nothing
Lack of confidence
I guess it's my so-called "academic anxiety" I'm badly afraid of failure; failing my family, friends and society
Multiple tasks/projects
So far, the various challenges I'm immersed right now in achieving my academic well-being is balancing my time in studies and family time
The different activities and celebrations our school is implementing for it challenges sportmanship and academic excellence
Feeling tired and lack of sleep
My inability to multi-task
Some challenges are sometimes meeting the deadlines together with term exam I am still in the process of taking the course by working hard and to earn my diploma and pass it to my parents as a change of their sacrifice and patience
I always follow what my parents want even If I don't like it
complex activities that I doubt it if it can help in the future. Activities that I am forced to do.
The unending requirements that should be passed on time because it gives me a hard time in achieving my academic well-being as a student
Time management
Because of my parents' sacrifice time management
asking something about my problem that hinders Financial problems
Sleepless nights
The challenge takes place not on financial difficulty but wishing the importance of it with my religious obligation, wherein whatever it takes
encountering friends at school
Terror teachers who aren't even teaching well
Clinical instructor who degraded me
I received so much hate from students, I don't even interact with. I am being judged and misunderstood by many.
Laziness and depression through academics
Living with my own family makes things easier for me because you always feel their support and they are always there to help you when you need them.
Going home once a week makes me exhausted and can't study instead here in Bayombong.
I have no problems with my family but I have difficulties in my studies because of the pressure and also financial problems
as a student, the challenges are time management and distracted sometimes and can't focus rarely
I am very lazy when it comes to studying and I lack focus
It is great that we are still complete and that we always support each other
I am challenged physically, mentally and emotionally because college is so hard Responsibilities, expectations and laziness
Fear of failing
Financial problems
My laziness and self-doubt
The various challenges I am immersed to in achieving my academic well-being as a student is balancing my day to day activities. Also, the way I manage my free time I don't know what my priority is.
Financially and even the time management because I encounter it a lot when it is needed. So I need to do my very best to use it in the right way.
Laziness
It's when I got a line of 7 in a major subject which was my first time. When I am always going to school
It's great to live my complete family because you always feel love Responsibilities at home and also family issues like the financially Financial needs and health
My goals are centered on my mom on it thinking of her sacrifices. Also our financial status is a factor.
Overall, I am okay
Such as having the course I am taking without my outmost likeness

My father's death, financial problems, and technology as a distraction to learning. Financial status
My family motivates me Financial problems
When I feel emotionally exhausted with my studies sometimes I don't even care if I fail my subjects
Deadly deadlines and the course I am in is not the course I can feel well of life and passion
as a student I have a problem in dealing with my academics because I do not know how to manage my
time
lack time and too much requirements on school project and also failures
I guess I don't have various challenges that I experiences in achieving my academic well-being because I
am completely fine with my family
The various challenges I am immersed to in achieving my academic well-being as a
student is managing my time because sometimes I don't know how manage my time
properly
I have 3 siblings. I am the 4th and the youngest. The 2 boys are already living on their own. Almost not
giving help to my mother. So I am encouraged to study well to help her.
financial because of the reason that my grandparents are only farmers
Dealing with a lot of people and participating events thjat contribute nothing to my grades
homesickness because of the distance from my home town
The challenge that immersed me in achieving my academic well-being as a student is being not too
confident with my ideas
when there is misunderstanding between members of my family Financial problems. My parents loan
I don't like the location of my school because it is too far from my hometown. I like the school but not its
location
insufficient focus, because there are many disturbances/hindrances in the society
I am lazy
being anxious and depressed
I fell asleep fast, I often so that was the challenge for me. I do a lot of sleep challenges that immersed to in
achieving my academic is failure
Challenges, I am push through my limits so that I can do more things
My brother ruins my review sometimes
Comparing, when they compare me. I treat it as a challenge for me to study more Time management,
involvement in extra-curricular activities and good cooperation during activities at school are some of the
challenges I face as a student
Too much requirements and lack of help
hectic schedule
everything get nothing is achieved Being away from home
Being with my friends that we can share knowledge about academics
Environment!!! Toxic environment, great teachers but not so great regarding my classmates
Incoming deadlines on requirements, paperworks at school that I forgot to sleep and eat
Absence of parents physically for they are both OFWs
One of the challenge that immersed me in achieving my academic well-being is the lack of support from
my family
I have a hard time managing everything since I'm a working For me I think is the financial
My father's trust on me. Especially his expectations and his set standards procrastination, laziness and
mental health
some of the subjects is hard
my classmates, time management and extracurricular acts which in turn, balancing my academic well-
being
Procrastination would be one of it. But sometimes I don't do that because there os a need to get
comfortable in the field of education
Time management, I have trouble in managing my time because of procrastination There are times I need
more time to finish my projects and assignemnts, lack of money to purchase what I need
Bunch of projects and assignments; small span of time achieving these Parents are a bit too strict
emotional imbalance; procrastination; addiction to technology
The various challenges I am immersed in achieving my academic well-being as a student is the
expectations sometimes
Managing time is always a problem, groupmates are another challenge and unproductive individuals.
Having negative thought that I can't do this and that

As a student sometimes I feel disappointed with my performance in school because even if I do my best I feel like it's not enough. Some of my teachers as well don't give grades that students deserve because they have favouritism

Procrastination! But my parents are always reminding me to do better!

as a student I face various challenges which is the presence of my family they are away from me because I need to study here for my future

For we as a student, the various challenges is being slow learner and it is hard to cope

For me my challenges in achieving my academic well-being is my family because I missed them a lot.

They are my source of strength

I am immersed to such critical thinking tasks in school, I experience difficulty about that, however, I need to comply because the teachers see this as a means to be a holistically developed student

The various challenges that I encountered in achieving my academic well-being are the many obligations at school and at home

Pressure and procrastination

sometimes, I feel discouraged and I doubt my capabilities, I procrastinate all the time and sometimes or always I feel so drained because of stress and sleepless nights

I vigorously study my lessons for major examinations by setting my priorities and sacrificing my comfort factors such as hanging out with friends and study instead demands of the society and school requirements

Being away from my family when I'm sick no one helps me which affects my grades.

Though I can't ask for more because they're giving their best which inspires me in my academics

various challenges that I immersed is to wake up early

challenge of time. Balancing times in doing what I love and doing what I must

Because we are the first batch in K-12. we struggle with the new curriculum we don't have a source e need to learn in our own study habits

I'm not open with my parents and it's hard for me because all of my problems, I always keep it to myself

As a students, struggles are common, but we need to become numb and just focus on what we are doing having a complicated family, because when studying I can't help to take it to my mind

the different subjects that we are taking and the different people I encounter everyday

For me is the load of subjects given to us, it was hard to manage since we are fully loaded

Financial and out of consideration of some teachers. Some teachers don't have the means of motivating some students and they have favoritism when it comes to students

Pressure is the most challenging. I immersed in my academic well-being Too high grade to achieve

Academic stress

being pessimistic

When there are conflicts on our family My time and finances

I experience failure

Having no time to breathe, high expectation, no room to mess up, pressure Time management

as a student I am challenged how to pass the cut-off

The challenge of balancing my studies with my own well-being constant failures and no support from family

Trying to maintain a good grade

Failures and many assignments and requirements at the same time

I guess that is happiness. I feel like I am not happy in what am I doing it feels like I am longing for something, yet I am still continuing it

sometimes I feel like the money that my parents pay for my tuition is not worth it

anymore because of the low scores I get sometimes in accounting but still I stand tall and look forward that someday I will be successful

The challenge is that my family has hopes and confidence in me which makes me pressured

as a BSA student the most challenging for me is maintaining my grades because of the cut-off

I am stressed and pressured

Procrastination, a lot of responsibilities that seek the same amount of attention I am pressured

it is difficult for us to bring back the enthusiasm I have in studying.

sometimes I feel like the money that my parents pay for my tuition is not worth it

anymore because of the low scores I get sometimes in accounting but still I stand tall and look forward that someday I will be successful

I am stressed and pressured
 Procrastination, a lot of responsibilities that seek the same amount of attention I am pressured
 as a student I am challenged how to pass the cutoff
 The challenge of balancing my studies with my own well-being constant failures and no support from
 family
 I am an active member of the school publication and I am experiencing difficulties in balancing my
 commitments in the organization and in my academics officially that accountancy is a very tough course
 The anxiety of failing and being far from home
 I think it's about balancing my times and time management in doing things parent pressure, not enough
 materials to review on
 Being away from them and the feeling of having someone to talk to personally and not on phone

APPENDIX 2: SURVEY CHECKLIST

Dear Respondent,

Greetings of Peace!

Humbly, we ask your consent to participate in our current research on
 “Intergenerational Relationships and Academic well-being: Case of Sophomore Students
 in a Catholic University. Rest assured that your answers shall be kept confidential. Thank
 you.

Respectfully yours,

Liberty A. Rosario, AB, BSED, LPT, MA, PhD

Candido Joseph T. Rosario Jr., RCE, MBA, MECE Henry F. Gamboa, AB, MA, PhD

Judith P. Daguio, BSED, MAED

CONSENT FORM

I am willing to participate as respondent of the current study
 with the assurance that data to be gathered shall be kept confidential.

Signature

FOUR Rs of INTERGENERATIONAL RELATIONSHIP AND LEVELS OF ACADEMIC WELL-BEING

Name : _____

Check your answer/s on the items provided:

Program:

BSED and BEED	
BSCE	
BSA	
BSN	

Intergenerational Relationships:

Living with parents	
Living with older siblings	
Living with grandparents	

Sex:

Male	
Female	

VERY WEAK	(1) VW	
WEAK	(2) W	
STRONG	(3) S	
VERY STRONG	(4) VS	

A. FOUR Rs OF INTERGENERATIONAL RELATIONSHIPS

RESPECT	1	2	3	4
1. I experience respect and acceptance from my parents, older siblings and grandparents.				
2. I manifest respect in my dealings to everyone at home .				
3. I can closely relate with my parents as I am respected of who I am				
4. I am fully accepted and valued with my own personhood at home .				
5. I enjoy the company of everyone home as there is equity .				
6. I am highly regarded with my dignity by everyone at home .				
7. I am not hostile keeping in touch to everyone at home.				
8. I am emotionally stable opening up to my parents, older siblings and grandparents.				
9. I feel belongingness at home where I experience recognition of my strengths and understanding of my weaknesses .				
10/ I have a voice and the ability to raise concerns and have these concerns addressed as I feel loved, valued and respected.				
RESPONSIBILITY				
1 . I have a safe, stable and supportive home environment with everyone in the family.				
2. I have the ability to respond in any circumstance at home.				
3. I feel valued performing my duty at home.				
4. I am willing to perform my duties and obligation at home .				
5. I have positive sense of culture and identity.				
6. I experience equity in term of rights and privileges.				
7. I accomplish my tasks and assignments as a child and a student without being forced.				
8. I am treated kindly and nicely as a person by everyone as there is shared responsibility.				
9. I can relate positively with others in accomplishing my responsibilities like giving care and support to everyone .				
10. I share common goals and objectives with everyone at home .				
RECIPROCITY				
1. I experience reciprocal love with everyone at home				
2. I am consintently keeping in touch with my parents , siblings and grandparents/				
3. I feel sense of belongingness at home.				
4. I experience harmony staying at home .				
5. I am willing to take care and attend to concerns at home				
6. I experience two -way attention at home.				
7. I am inspired by my parents, older siblings and grandparents to be best that I can as a person.				
8. I enjoy my grandparents with my day to day encounters.				
9. I am allowed exercise autonomy in making my decisions.				
10. I do things for everyone reciprocally at home.				
RESILIENCE				
1. I find my family very supportive of me even in most difficult times.				
2. I am assured of enduring love, support from everyone at home.				
3. I experience solidarity at home even in the midst of challenges and untoward				
4. I have strength hope and vigor to confront problems ahead.				
5. I can withstand the test of time as I feel supported.				
6. I have sense of courage shared with everyone in facing the challenges of life.				
7. I have deep sense of trust accorded to my family and God in most challenging				
8. I experience unwavering support and understanding at home .				
9. I am assured that my parents, older siblings and grandparents think about my				
10. I can manage strategies which are responsive to our needs at home especially				

B. OVER-ALL QUALITY ON THE 4RS OF INTERGENERATIONAL RELATIONSHIPS

1. I experience respect is deeply imbedded in all my intergenerational relationships at home.				
2. I feel sense of responsibility in sustaining my family.				
3. I manifest reciprocity in my dealings to my parents, older children, grandparents and sibling				
4. I find resilience in the family as shown by my parents, older children, grandparents and siblings especially during difficult times.				

C. ACADEMIC WELL-BEING

1.	I experience vigor and inspiration to accomplish my tasks and responsibilities as a student.				
2.	I feel engaged with all the undertakings I have in school.				
3.	I experience balance between my academic life and intergenerational relationships.				
4.	I am bursting with energy when I am doing my work academically.				
5.	I am enthusiastic about my studies as I get full support at home and in school.				
6.	I am happy relating with others in school.				
7.	I am capable of doing more complicated assignments in class if I try hard enough.				
8.	I feel emotionally drained and exhausted with my studies.				
9.	I doubt the significance of my studies.				
10.	I feel happy embracing the four pillars of education such as learning to know, learning to do, learning to relate with others and learning to be.				

D. . What are your personal experiences on intergenerational relationships in the family that influence your academic well-being?

E. What are the various challenges you are immersed to in achieving your academic well-being as student?
